

Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 3 up to 9

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Inder Taneja published two papers on Zenodo (combining results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
18-01-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ²⁸
03-02-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20000 to 30000 ²⁹

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵
28-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (03) ²⁵
06-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (04) ³⁰
07-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (05) ³¹

Historic Overview

Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases ¹⁶

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 11 through 16):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (completing the base 11 up to 16 series):

Date	Title
09-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX) ²³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (extending the base 16 series):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFF) ²⁴

Authors published two papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 17 through 62):

Date	Title
23-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to #####) ²⁶
02-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 62 (0000 up to #####) ²⁷

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 7 through 9):

Date	Title
13-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 9 (0000 up to 8888) ³²
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 8 (0000 up to 7777) ³³
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 7 (0000 up to 6666) ³⁴

Base 9 Crazy Sequential Representation

For example, two valid base 9 crazy sequential representations:

23_{10} 25_9	36_{10} 40_9
$1_9/2_9*((-3_9+4_9)^5+67_9)-8_9$	$(8_9-7_9)^6*(-5_9+43_9)+2_9/1_9$

For clarity, the corresponding base 10 representations:

$1_{10}/2_{10}*((-3_{10}+4_{10})^5+61_{10})-8_{10}$	$(8_{10}-7_{10})^6*(-5_{10}+39_{10})+2_{10}/1_{10}$
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Definition

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	+	-	*	/	^	()
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	-----

Digits 1 up to 8 occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$1/2*((-3+4)^5+67)-8$	$(8-7)^6*(-5+43)+2/1$
-----------------------	-----------------------

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$1/2*((-3+4)^5+67)-8$	$(8-7)^6*(-5+43)+2/1$
-----------------------	-----------------------

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$1/2*((-3+4)^5+67)-8$	$(8-7)^6*(-5+43)+2/1$
-----------------------	-----------------------

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$1/2*((-3+4)^5+67)-8$	$(8-7)^6*(-5+43)+2/1$
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Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$1/2*((-3+4)^5+67)-8$	$(8-7)^6*(-5+43)+2/1$
-----------------------	-----------------------

Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$(1+2-3)*(45*(-(6^7)+8))$	$(8+7*-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45/-(6^7)+8)$	$(8+7/-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45^-(6^7)+8)$	$(8+7^-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(-(1+2)+3)*(45^(6^7)+8)$	$(8+7^(6^5)+4)*(-(3-2)+1)$
$-(1-2+24*(5-6-7+8))$	$-((8-7-6+5)*43-2+1)$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Base 8 Crazy Sequential Representation

For example, two valid base 8 crazy sequential representations:

$$\begin{array}{c} 27_{10} \quad 33_8 \\ \hline -1_8/2_8*((-3_8+4_8)^5-67_8) \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} 5_{10} \quad 5_8 \\ \hline 7_8+(6_8-5_8)^4 3_8*2_8/-1_8 \end{array}$$

For clarity, the corresponding base 10 representations:

$$\begin{array}{c} -1_{10}/2_{10}*((-3_{10}+4_{10})^5-55_{10}) \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} 7_{10}+(6_{10}-5_{10})^4 35_{10}*2_{10}/-1_{10} \end{array}$$

Definition

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

$$\begin{array}{c} 1 \quad 2 \quad 3 \quad 4 \quad 5 \quad 6 \quad 7 \quad + \quad - \quad * \quad / \quad ^ \quad (\quad) \end{array}$$

Digits 1 up to 7 occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$$\begin{array}{c} -1/2*((-3+4)^5-67) \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} 7+(6-5)^4 3*2/-1 \end{array}$$

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$$\begin{array}{c} -1/2*((-3+4)^5-67) \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} 7+(6-5)^4 3*2/-1 \end{array}$$

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$$\begin{array}{c} -1/2*((-3+4)^5-67) \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} 7+(6-5)^4 3*2/-1 \end{array}$$

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$$\begin{array}{c} -1/2*((-3+4)^5-67) \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} 7+(6-5)^4 3*2/-1 \end{array}$$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$$\begin{array}{c} -1/2*((-3+4)^5-67) \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} 7+(6-5)^4 3*2/-1 \end{array}$$

Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$$\begin{array}{c} (1+2-3)*45^*(6^7) \\ (1+2-3)*45/-(6^7) \\ (1+2-3)*45^-(6^7) \\ -(1+2)+3)*45^(6+7) \\ -(1^2^3*(4-5-6+7)) \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} 76^*(5^4)*(3-2-1) \\ 76/-(5^4)*(3-2-1) \\ 76^-(5^4)*(3-2-1) \\ 76^(5+4)*(-(3-2)+1) \\ -((7-6-5+4)*3^2^1) \end{array}$$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Base 7 Crazy Sequential Representation

For example, two valid base 7 crazy sequential representations:

$$\begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{45_{10} \quad 63_7}} \\ -12_7 * ((-3_7 + 4_7)^{5_7 - 6_7}) \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{7_{10} \quad 10_7}} \\ (-6_7 + 5_7)^{4_7 - 3_7} * 2_7 / -1_7 \end{array}$$

For clarity, the corresponding base 10 representations:

$$\underline{\underline{-9_{10} * ((-3_{10} + 4_{10})^{5_{10} - 6_{10}})}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(-6_{10} + 5_{10})^{4_{10} - 3_{10}} * 2_{10} / -1_{10}}}$$

Definition

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

$$\underline{\underline{1 \quad 2 \quad 3 \quad 4 \quad 5 \quad 6 \quad + \quad - \quad * \quad / \quad ^ \quad (\quad)}}$$

Digits 1 up to 6 occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$$\underline{\underline{-12 * ((-3 + 4)^{5 - 6})}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(-6 + 5)^{4 - 3} * 2 / -1}}$$

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$$\underline{\underline{-12 * ((-3 + 4)^{5 - 6})}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(-6 + 5)^{4 - 3} * 2 / -1}}$$

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$$\underline{\underline{-12 * ((-3 + 4)^{5 - 6})}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(-6 + 5)^{4 - 3} * 2 / -1}}$$

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$$\underline{\underline{-12 * ((-3 + 4)^{5 - 6})}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(-6 + 5)^{4 - 3} * 2 / -1}}$$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$$\underline{\underline{-12 * ((-3 + 4)^{5 - 6})}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(-6 + 5)^{4 - 3} * 2 / -1}}$$

Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$$\begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{(1 + 2 - 3) * 4 * -(5^6)}} \\ \underline{\underline{(1 + 2 - 3) * 4 / -(5^6)}} \\ \underline{\underline{(1 + 2 - 3) * 4 ^ -(5^6)}} \\ \underline{\underline{(-(1 + 2) + 3) * 4 ^ (5 + 6)}} \\ \underline{\underline{-(1^2 * (3 - 4 - 5 + 6))}} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{6 * -(5^4) * (3 - 2 - 1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{6 / -(5^4) * (3 - 2 - 1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{6 ^ -(5^4) * (3 - 2 - 1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{6 ^ (5 + 4) * (-(3 - 2) + 1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{-((6 - 5 - 4 + 3) * 2^1)}} \end{array}$$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

First Integers / Listings

The “first integers that can not be sequentially represented under the defined operations” were identified “through brute force search” by Tim Wylie¹⁶ and published on arXiv:

Base	Increasing	Decreasing	Neither
3	0	0	0
4	13	11	16
5	27	17	27
6	67	77	92
7	260	262	292
8	614	809	1192
9	3293	4570	5414
10	10958	14324	21212

Tim Wylie¹⁶ allowed “negation of an expression” during brute force search. In contrast, authors^{32,33,34} limited brute force search to “genuine” crazy sequential representations, which by definition do not allow “negation of an expression”. Nevertheless, identical “first integers” were identified, namely:

Base	Increasing	Decreasing	Neither
7	$521_7 = 260_{10}$	$523_7 = 262_{10}$	$565_7 = 292_{10}$
8	$1146_8 = 614_{10}$	$1451_8 = 809_{10}$	$2250_8 = 1192_{10}$
9	$4458_9 = 3293_{10}$	$6237_9 = 4570_{10}$	$7375_9 = 5414_{10}$

Tim Wylie¹⁶ listed “the first 40” for base 5 up to 7 and “the first 20” for base 8 and 9. In contrast, authors^{32,33,34} listed available “genuine” crazy sequential representations for base 7 (from 0_7 up to 6666_7), base 8 (from 0_8 up to 7777_8) and base 9 (from 0_9 up to 8888_9).

Results

In case brute force search is limited to “genuine” crazy sequential representations, the “first integers” hold true for base three up to six as well, see supplement one.

Base	Increasing	Decreasing	Neither
3	$0_3 = 0_{10}$	$0_3 = 0_{10}$	$0_3 = 0_{10}$
4	$31_4 = 13_{10}$	$23_4 = 11_{10}$	$100_4 = 16_{10}$
5	$102_5 = 27_{10}$	$32_5 = 17_{10}$	$102_5 = 27_{10}$
6	$151_6 = 67_{10}$	$205_6 = 77_{10}$	$232_5 = 92_{10}$

Authors provide a non-exhaustive list with “genuine” crazy sequential representations for base three up to six (from 0_{10} up to 2147483647_{10}), see supplement two.

Note

Authors consider genuine crazy sequential representations to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial. Authors did not simplify and/or optimize the crazy sequential representations.

Authors do not guaranty:

- Published crazy sequential representations are the shortest in existence.
- Published crazy sequential representations are in their simplest form.
- Unavailable crazy sequential representations do not exists.

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A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 18 Feb 2019

Supplement 1

Base 3	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0000	0000	?	?
0001	0001	(1^2)	$(2-1)$
0002	0002	(1^2)	(2^*1)
0010	0003	$(1+2)$	$(2+1)$
0011	0004	?	?

Base 4	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0000	0000	$((1+2)-3)$	$(3-(2+1))$
0001	0001	(1^23)	$(3/(2+1))$
0002	0002	$(12/3)$	$((3-2)+1)$
0003	0003	$(12-3)$	$(3^*(2-1))$
0010	0004	$((1^2)+3)$	$((3+2)-1)$
0011	0005	$((1^2)+3)$	$((3+2)^*1)$
0012	0006	$((1+2)+3)$	$(-3+21)$
0013	0007	$(1+(2^*3))$	$((3^2)+1)$
0020	0008	$((1^2)^3)$	$((3^2)-1)$
0021	0009	$(12+3)$	$(3^*(2+1))$
0022	0010	$(-1+23)$	$((3^2)+1)$
0023	0011	(1^*23)	?
0030	0012	$(1+23)$	$(3+21)$
0031	0013	?	$(32-1)$
0032	0014	?	(32^*1)
0033	0015	?	$(32+1)$
0100	0016	?	?

Base 5	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0000	0000	$(12-(3+4))$	$((4-(3+2))+1)$
0001	0001	(1^234)	$((4-3)^21)$
0002	0002	$((1^2)^3)/4)$	$((4-3)^2)^*1)$
0003	0003	$((-1+23)/4)$	$((4-3)+2)^*1)$
0004	0004	$((1^23)^*4)$	$((-4-3)+21)$
0010	0005	$((1^23)+4)$	$(4+(3/(2+1)))$
0011	0006	$(12+3)-4)$	$((4^3/2)^*1)$
0012	0007	$(12^*(-3+4))$	$((4^3/2)+1)$
0013	0008	$((12-3)+4)$	$(4^(3/2))^*1)$
0014	0009	$((1^*23)-4)$	$((4+3)+2)^*1)$
0020	0010	$((1+23)-4)$	$((-4+3)+21)$
0021	0011	$((1+(2^*3))+4)$	$(4-3)^*21)$
0022	0012	$(-12+34)$	$(43-21)$
0023	0013	$((1+2)^3)+4)$	$((-4+32)^*1)$
0024	0014	$((12+3)+4)$	$((-4+32)+1)$
0030	0015	$((1+2)+(3^*4))$	$((4+3)^2)+1)$
0031	0016	$((12-3)^*4)$	$(4^*((3+2)-1))$
0032	0017	$((1^*23)+4)$	?
0033	0018	$((1+23)+4)$	$((4+3)+21)$
0034	0019	$(12+(3^*4))$	$((4^*(3+2))-1)$
0040	0020	$((1^2)+34)$	$(43-(2+1))$
0041	0021	$((1^2)+34)$	$((4+32)^*1)$
0042	0022	$((1+2)+34)$	$((4+32)+1)$
0043	0023	$((1+2)^3)-4)$	$(4^3)+21)$
0044	0024	$((1+2)+3)^*4)$	$((43+2)-1)$
0100	0025	$((12^*3)+4)$	$((43+2)^*1)$
0101	0026	$(12+34)$	$((43+2)+1)$
0102	0027	?	?

Base 6	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0000	0000	$((1^{23}+4)-5)$	$(54*(3-(2+1)))$
0001	0001	(1^{2345})	$((5-4)^{321})$
0002	0002	$(12^{(3/(4+5))})$	$((5^4/32)+1)$
0003	0003	$((12+3)+4)/5$	$(5/((4/(3^2))+1))$
0004	0004	$((-1^{234})+5)$	$((5+(4^3))-21)$
0005	0005	$((1^{234})^5)$	$(-54+(3^21))$
0010	0006	$((12+34)/5)$	$(5*((4/32)+1))$
0011	0007	$(12+((3-4)^5))$	$(54-(3^{(2+1)}))$
0012	0008	$(12*((-3+4)^5))$	$(5*(-4+3)+21)$
0013	0009	$((-12+34)-5)$	$((-5+43)-21)$
0014	0010	$((1^{23}+4)+5)$	$((5^4+3)-21)$
0015	0011	$((123+4)/5)$	$((5-(4+3))+21)$
0020	0012	$((1^*23^*4)/5)$	$((-5+43)/2)+1$
0021	0013	$((-1-23)+45)$	$(54-(32+1))$
0022	0014	$((-1^*23)+45)$	$((54-32)^*1)$
0023	0015	$((1-23)+45)$	$((54-32)+1)$
0024	0016	$((1/2)^*34)+5$	$((5+43)/2)^*1$
0025	0017	$((1+23)-4)+5$	$((5+43)/2)+1$
0030	0018	$((-12-3)+45)$	$(54-(3+21))$
0031	0019	$((1+234)/5)$	$((5+43)-21)$
0032	0020	$((12+3)+4)+5$	$((5/4)^*(3+21))$
0033	0021	$((1^{23})+(4^*5))$	$((5-4)+32)^*1$
0034	0022	$(123-45)$	$((5-4)+32)+1$
0035	0023	$((12^*3)+4)-5$	$((-5+43)+2)-1$
0040	0024	$((-12+3)+45)$	$(54+3)-21$
0041	0025	$((12+34)-5)$	$((5/4)^*32)^*1$
0042	0026	$((1-2)+34)+5$	$((5/4)^*32)+1$
0043	0027	$((1^2)^*34)+5$	$(54-((3^2)+1))$
0044	0028	$((-1^{23})+45)$	$(54-((3+2)+1))$
0045	0029	$((1^{23})^45)$	$((5+4)+32)^*1$
0050	0030	$((1^{23})+45)$	$((5+4)+32)+1$
0051	0031	$(123-(4^*5))$	$((5+43)-2)+1$
0052	0032	$((1^2)^*3)+45$	$(5+43)^*(2-1)$
0053	0033	$((12^*3)+4)+5$	$((54-3)+2)^*1$
0054	0034	$(12-3)+45$	$(54^*3)/(2+1)$
0055	0035	$(12+34)+5$	$((-5+43)+21)$
0100	0036	$((1+23)+(4^*5))$	$((5^4+3)+21)$
0101	0037	$((1^*2)^3)+45$	$(54+3)^*(2-1)$
0102	0038	$((1+2)^*3)+45$	$((54+3)+2)-1$
0103	0039	$((12+3)^*4)-5$	$((54+3)+2)^*1$
0104	0040	$(12+3)+45$	$((54+3)+2)+1$
0105	0041	$((1+2)^*3)^*4)+5$	$(54+(3^2)+1)$
0110	0042	$(123-(4+5))$	$(54+(3^2))-1$
0111	0043	$((-1+23)+45)$	$(54+(3*(2+1)))$
0112	0044	$(1^*23)+45$	$(54-3)+21$
0113	0045	$(1+23)+45$	$(5+43)+21$
0114	0046	$(12*((3/4)+5))$	$((-5+(4^3))-21)$
0115	0047	$(1+(2*(3+(4^*5))))$	$((5^4)^*3)-21$
0120	0048	$(12*((-3+4)+5))$	$(5+4)+(3^21)$
0121	0049	$((12+3)^*4)+5$	$((-5+(43^2))^*1)$
0122	0050	$(123+4)-5$	$(54+3)+21$
0123	0051	$(123*(-4+5))$	$((54^*3)/2)^*1$
0124	0052	$(123-4)+5$	$((54^*3)/2)+1$
0125	0053	$(12^*3)+45$	$(54+32)-1$
0130	0054	$(1^*2)^*(34+5)$	$(54+32)^*1$
0131	0055	$(1+(2*(34+5)))$	$(54+32)+1$
0132	0056	$((1+2)^3)+45$	$(5+(4^3))-21$
0133	0057	$((-1-2)+(3^*4)^5)$	$((5^4)^*3)-(2+1)$
0134	0058	$((1-2)+3)^*45$	$(5+(43^2))-1$
0135	0059	$((1+23)^*4)-5$	$(5+(43^2))^*1$
0140	0060	$(123+4)+5$	$(5+(43^2))+1$
0141	0061	$(12*(3+4))+5$	$(54+(3^{(2+1)}))$
0142	0062	$(1234/5)$	$((54-3)^2)^*1$
0143	0063	$(-1+(2*(3+45)))$	$((54-3)^2)+1$
0144	0064	$(1^*2)^*(3+45)$	$((5+43)^2)^*1$
0145	0065	$((1^*23)^*4)+5$	$((5+43)^2)+1$
0150	0066	$(1+(23^*4))+5$	$((-5+43)^*(2+1))$
0151	0067	?	$((5+(4^3))-2)^*1$
0152	0068	$(12+((3^*4)^5))$	$54*((3-2)+1)$
0153	0069	$((1+23)^*4)+5$	$(543/(2+1))$
0154	0070	$((-12+34)^5)$	$(5*(43-21))$

Base 6	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0155	0071	$(123+(4*5))$	$(-5+(4*(32-1)))$
0200	0072	$((1*2)^3*(4+5))$	$((-5+(4^3))+21)$
0201	0073	$(1+((2^3)*(4+5)))$	$(54+(3*21))$
0202	0074	$((-1*2)+(3^4))-5$	$((54+3)^2)*1$
0203	0075	$((12+3)+4)*5$	$((54+3)^2)+1$
0204	0076	$((1^2)*3)^4-5$	$(-5+(43*(2+1)))$
0205	0077	$((1^2)+(3^4))-5$	?
0210	0078	$(-12+(3^4))+5$	$((5+4)-3)*21$
0211	0079	$(-12+(3^45))$	$(-5+(4*(32+1)))$
0212	0080	$(123+45)$	$(5*(-4+32))*1$
0213	0081	$((1+2)*(34+5))$	$(5+(4*(32-1)))$
0214	0082	?	$(5+(4^3))+21$
0215	0083	$((-1-2)+(3^4))+5$	?
0220	0084	$((12+(3^4))-5)$	$((5+(4*32))-1)$
0221	0085	$((-1*2)+(3^45))$	$54*((3/2)+1)$
0222	0086	$((1-2)+(3^45))$	$(5+(43*(2+1)))$
0223	0087	$((1^2)*3)^45$	$(-54+321)$
0224	0088	$((-1+234)-5)$	?
0225	0089	$((1*234)-5)$	$((54*3)-21)$
0230	0090	$((1+234)-5)$	$((5+4)*(-3+21))$
0231	0091	$((12*3)^4)-5$	$((-5+(4*3))^21)$
0232	0092	?	?

Supplement 2

Base 3	Base 10	Increasing
000000000000002	00000000002	(1^*2)
000000000000010	00000000003	$(1+2)$
000000000000012	00000000005	12

Base 3	Base 10	Decreasing
000000000000002	00000000002	(2^*1)
000000000000010	00000000003	$(2+1)$
000000000000021	00000000007	21

Base 4	Base 10	Increasing
000000000000002	00000000002	$(12/3)$
000000000000003	00000000003	$(12-3)$
000000000000010	00000000004	$((1^*2)+3)$
000000000000011	00000000005	$((1^*2)+3)$
000000000000012	00000000006	$((1+2)+3)$
000000000000013	00000000007	$(1+(2^*3))$
000000000000020	00000000008	$((1^*2)^*3)$
000000000000021	00000000009	$(12+3)$
000000000000022	00000000010	$(-1+23)$
000000000000023	00000000011	(1^*23)
000000000000030	00000000012	$(1+23)$
000000000000102	00000000018	(12^*3)
000000000000123	00000000027	$((1+2)^*3)$
000000000000123	00000000027	123
0000000000003120	00000000216	(12^*3)

Base 4	Base 10	Decreasing
000000000000002	00000000002	$((3-2)+1)$
000000000000003	00000000003	$(3^*(2-1))$
000000000000010	00000000004	$((3+2)-1)$
000000000000011	00000000005	$((3+2)^*1)$
000000000000012	00000000006	$(-3+21)$
000000000000013	00000000007	$((3^*2)+1)$
000000000000020	00000000008	$((3^*2)-1)$
000000000000021	00000000009	$(3^*(2+1))$
000000000000022	00000000010	$((3^*2)+1)$
000000000000030	00000000012	$(3+21)$
000000000000031	00000000013	$(32-1)$
000000000000032	00000000014	(32^*1)
000000000000033	00000000015	$(32+1)$
000000000000123	00000000027	(3^*21)
000000000000321	00000000057	321
000000010303203	00000019683	(3^*21)

Base 5	Base 10	Increasing
00000000000002	0000000002	$((1^2)^3)/4$
00000000000003	0000000003	$((-1+23)/4)$
00000000000004	0000000004	$((1^23)^4)$
00000000000010	0000000005	$((1^23)+4)$
00000000000011	0000000006	$((12+3)-4)$
00000000000012	0000000007	$(12^*(-3+4))$
00000000000013	0000000008	$((12-3)+4)$
00000000000014	0000000009	$((1^*23)-4)$
00000000000020	0000000010	$((1+23)-4)$
00000000000021	0000000011	$((1+(2^*3))+4)$
00000000000022	0000000012	$((-12+34)$
00000000000023	0000000013	$((1+2)^*3)+4)$
00000000000024	0000000014	$((12+3)+4)$
00000000000030	0000000015	$((1+2)+(3^*4))$
00000000000031	0000000016	$((12-3)^*4)$
00000000000032	0000000017	$((1^*23)+4)$
00000000000033	0000000018	$((1+23)+4)$
00000000000034	0000000019	$(12+(3^*4))$
00000000000040	0000000020	$((1^2)+34)$
00000000000041	0000000021	$((1^*2)+34)$
00000000000042	0000000022	$((1+2)+34)$
00000000000043	0000000023	$((1+2)^3)-4)$
00000000000044	0000000024	$((1+2+3)^*4)$
00000000000100	0000000025	$((12^*3)+4)$
00000000000101	0000000026	$(12+34)$
00000000000103	0000000028	$((1+(2^*3))^*4)$
00000000000111	0000000031	$((1+2)^3)+4)$
00000000000112	0000000032	$((1^2)^3)^*4)$
00000000000113	0000000033	$(1+((2^3)^*4))$
00000000000114	0000000034	$(123-4)$
00000000000121	0000000036	$((1+2)^*3)^*4)$
00000000000122	0000000037	$((-1+(2^*34))$
00000000000123	0000000038	$((1^*2)^*34)$
00000000000124	0000000039	$(1+(2^*34))$
00000000000130	0000000040	$((12+3)^*4)$
00000000000132	0000000042	$(123+4)$
00000000000143	0000000048	$((-1+23)^*4)$
00000000000144	0000000049	$(12^*(3+4))$
00000000000201	0000000051	$((-1+(23^*4))$
00000000000202	0000000052	$((1^*23)^*4)$
00000000000203	0000000053	$(1+(23^*4))$
00000000000211	0000000056	$((1+23)^*4)$
00000000000212	0000000057	$((1+2)^*34)$
00000000000233	0000000068	$((-1+234)$
00000000000234	0000000069	(1^*234)
00000000000240	0000000070	$(1+234)$
00000000000244	0000000074	$((-12+(3^4))$
00000000000303	0000000078	$((-1-2)+(3^4))$
00000000000304	0000000079	$((-1^*2)+(3^4))$
00000000000310	0000000080	$((1-2)+(3^4))$
00000000000311	0000000081	$((1^2)^*3)^4)$
00000000000312	0000000082	$((1^2)+(3^4))$
00000000000313	0000000083	$((1^*2)+(3^4))$
00000000000314	0000000084	$((12^*3)^*4)$
00000000000323	0000000088	$(12+(3^4))$
00000000000413	0000000108	$((1+2)^3)^*4)$
000000000001002	0000000127	$((-1+(2^*(3+4)))$
000000000001003	0000000128	$((1^*2)^(3+4))$
000000000001004	0000000129	$(1+(2^(3+4)))$
000000000001013	0000000133	(12^*34)
000000000001102	0000000152	(123^*4)
000000000001121	0000000161	$((-1+(2^*(3^4)))$
000000000001122	0000000162	$((1^*2)^*(3^4))$
000000000001123	0000000163	$(1+(2^*(3^4)))$
000000000001234	0000000194	1234
000000000001433	0000000243	$((1+2)^*(3^4))$
000000000002011	0000000256	$((12-3)^4)$
000000000002324	0000000339	$((12^3)-4)$
000000000002342	0000000347	$((12^3)+4)$
000000000004232	0000000567	$(12^*(3^4))$
000000000004444	0000000624	$((-1+((2+3)^4))$

Base 5	Base 10	Increasing
00000000010000	0000000625	$((1^2)+3)^4$
00000000010001	0000000626	$(1+(2+3)^4)$
00000000020140	0000001295	$(-1+(2^*3)^4)$
00000000020141	0000001296	$((1+2)+3)^4$
00000000020142	0000001297	$(1+(2^*3)^4)$
00000000020442	0000001372	$(12^3)^4$
00000000032222	0000002187	$(1+2)^{(3+4)}$
00000000034101	0000002401	$(1+(2^*3))^4$
000000000112340	0000004095	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}(3^*4)))$
000000000112341	0000004096	$(1^2)^{(3^*4)}$
000000000112342	0000004097	$(1+(2^{\wedge}(3^*4)))$
000000000202221	0000006561	$((1+2)^*3)^4$
000000000310000	0000010000	$(12+3)^4$
000000001130421	0000020736	$(1-23)^4$
000000001403220	0000028560	$(-1+(23^4))$
000000001403221	0000028561	$(1^*23)^4$
000000001403222	0000028562	$(1+(23^4))$
000000002212131	0000038416	$(1+23)^4$
000000022210411	0000194481	$(12^*3)^4$
000000113234122	0000524287	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}34))$
000000113234123	0000524288	$(1^*2)^{\wedge}34$
000000113234124	0000524289	$(1+(2^{\wedge}34))$
000000114001231	0000531441	$(1+2)^{(3^*4)}$
000000202323133	0000823543	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))$
000001013211021	00002085136	(123^4)
004340014331332	01162261467	$(1+2)^{\wedge}34$

Base 5	Base 10	Decreasing
00000000000002	0000000002	$((4-3)^2)^*1$
00000000000003	0000000003	$((4-3)+2)^*1$
00000000000004	0000000004	$((-4-3)+21)$
00000000000010	0000000005	$4+(3/(2+1))$
00000000000011	0000000006	$((4^3)/2)^*1$
00000000000012	0000000007	$((4^3)/2)+1$
00000000000013	0000000008	$(4^{\wedge}(3/2))^*1$
00000000000014	0000000009	$((4+3)+2)^*1$
00000000000020	0000000010	$((-4+3)+21)$
00000000000021	0000000011	$(4-3)^*21$
00000000000022	0000000012	$43-21$
00000000000023	0000000013	$((-4+32)^*1)$
00000000000024	0000000014	$((-4+32)+1)$
00000000000030	0000000015	$((4+3)^2)+1$
00000000000031	0000000016	$4^*(3+2)-1$
00000000000033	0000000018	$(4+3)+21$
00000000000034	0000000019	$(4^*(3+2))-1$
00000000000040	0000000020	$43-(2+1)$
00000000000041	0000000021	$(4+32)^*1$
00000000000042	0000000022	$(4+32)+1$
00000000000043	0000000023	$(4^3)+21$
00000000000044	0000000024	$(43+2)-1$
00000000000100	0000000025	$(43+2)^*1$
000000000000101	0000000026	$(43+2)+1$
000000000000103	0000000028	$4^*((3^2)+1)$
000000000000104	0000000029	$-4+(3^*21)$
000000000000111	0000000031	$4+(3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
000000000000112	0000000032	$4^*(-3+21)$
000000000000113	0000000033	$((4^{\wedge}3)/2)+1$
000000000000114	0000000034	$43+21$
000000000000120	0000000035	$(4^*(3^{\wedge}2))-1$
000000000000121	0000000036	$(4^3)^*(2+1)$
000000000000122	0000000037	$4+(3^*21)$
000000000000130	0000000040	$4^*((3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
000000000000140	0000000045	$(43^2)-1$
000000000000141	0000000046	$(43^2)^*1$
000000000000142	0000000047	$(43^2)+1$
000000000000143	0000000048	$((4+3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
000000000000144	0000000049	$((4+3)^{\wedge}2)^*1$
000000000000200	0000000050	$((4+3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
000000000000203	0000000053	$(4^{\wedge}3)-21$
000000000000211	0000000056	$4^*(3+21)$
000000000000221	0000000061	$(4^{\wedge}3)-(2+1)$
000000000000222	0000000062	$((4^{\wedge}3)-2)^*1$
000000000000223	0000000063	$((4^{\wedge}3)-2)+1$
000000000000224	0000000064	$4^*(32-1)$
000000000000230	0000000065	$((4^{\wedge}3)+2)-1$
000000000000231	0000000066	$((4^{\wedge}3)+2)^*1$
000000000000232	0000000067	$(4^*32)-1$
000000000000233	0000000068	$(4^*32)^*1$
000000000000234	0000000069	$43^*(2+1)$
000000000000242	0000000072	$4^*(32+1)$
000000000000300	0000000075	$(4^{\wedge}3)+21$
000000000000302	0000000077	$(4+3)^*21$
000000000000312	0000000082	$(-4+321)$
000000000000330	0000000090	$4+321$
000000000000413	0000000108	$4^*(3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
000000000000431	0000000116	$432-1$
000000000000432	0000000117	432^*1
000000000000433	0000000118	$432+1$
000000000001002	0000000127	$((4^{\wedge}3)^2)-1$
000000000001003	0000000128	$((4^{\wedge}3)^2)^*1$
000000000001004	0000000129	$((4^{\wedge}3)^2)+1$
000000000001012	0000000132	$(4^3)^*21$
000000000001033	0000000143	$((4^3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
000000000001034	0000000144	$((4^3)^{\wedge}2)^*1$
000000000001040	0000000145	$((4^3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
000000000001232	0000000192	$(4^{\wedge}3)^*(2+1)$
000000000002003	0000000253	43^*21
000000000002011	0000000256	$4^{\wedge}((3+2)-1)$
000000000002333	0000000343	$((4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$

Base 5	Base 10	Decreasing
00000000002334	00000000344	$(4*321)$
00000000004103	00000000528	$((43^2)-1)$
00000000004104	00000000529	$((43^2)*1)$
00000000004110	00000000530	$((43^2)+1)$
00000000004321	00000000586	4321
00000000010304	00000000704	$((4^3)*21)$
00000000013043	00000001023	$((4^(3+2))-1)$
00000000013044	00000001024	$((4^(3+2))*1)$
00000000013100	00000001025	$((4^(3+2))+1)$
00000000023403	00000001728	$((4*3)^(2+1))$
000000000112340	00000004095	$((4^(3*2))-1)$
000000000112341	00000004096	$(4^((3+2)+1))$
000000000112342	00000004097	$((4^(3*2))+1)$
000000000342132	00000012167	$(43^(2+1))$
000000001011014	00000016384	$(4^((3*2)+1))$
000000004044121	00000065536	$(4^(-3+21))$
0000000021132033	00000177143	$(-4+(3^21))$
000000021132101	00000177151	$(4+(3^21))$
000000031342033	00000262143	$((4^(3^2))-1)$
000000031342034	00000262144	$(4^(3*(2+1)))$
000000031342040	00000262145	$((4^(3^2))+1)$
000000140133323	00000708588	$(4*(3^21))$
000000232023301	00001048576	$(4^((3^2)+1))$
001022204413311	00268435456	$(4^(3+21))$
013022143423433	01977326743	$((4+3)^21)$

Base 6	Base 10	Increasing
00000000000002	0000000002	$(12^{3/(4+5)})$
00000000000003	0000000003	$((12+3)+4)/5$
00000000000004	0000000004	$((-1^{234})+5)$
00000000000005	0000000005	$(1^{234})^{*5}$
00000000000010	0000000006	$(12+34)/5$
00000000000011	0000000007	$12+((3-4)^{5})$
00000000000012	0000000008	$12^{*}((-3+4)^{5})$
00000000000013	0000000009	$((-12+34)-5)$
00000000000014	0000000010	$((1^{23})+4)+5$
00000000000015	0000000011	$(123+4)/5$
00000000000020	0000000012	$((1^{*23})^{*4})/5$
00000000000021	0000000013	$((-1-23)+45)$
00000000000022	0000000014	$((-1^{*23})+45)$
00000000000023	0000000015	$(1-23)+45$
00000000000024	0000000016	$((1/2)^{*34})+5$
00000000000025	0000000017	$((1+23)-4)+5$
00000000000030	0000000018	$((-12-3)+45)$
00000000000031	0000000019	$(1+234)/5$
00000000000032	0000000020	$((12+3)+4)+5$
00000000000033	0000000021	$(1^{23})+(4^{*5})$
00000000000034	0000000022	$123-45$
00000000000035	0000000023	$((12^{*3})+4)-5$
00000000000040	0000000024	$((-12+3)+45)$
00000000000041	0000000025	$(12+34)-5$
00000000000042	0000000026	$((1-2)+34)+5$
00000000000043	0000000027	$((1^{2})^{*34})+5$
00000000000044	0000000028	$((-1^{23})+45)$
00000000000045	0000000029	$(1^{23})^{*45}$
00000000000050	0000000030	$(1^{23})+45$
00000000000051	0000000031	$123-(4^{*5})$
00000000000052	0000000032	$((1^{2})^{*3})+45$
00000000000053	0000000033	$((12^{*3})+4)+5$
00000000000054	0000000034	$(12-3)+45$
00000000000055	0000000035	$(12+34)+5$
00000000000100	0000000036	$(1+23)+(4^{*5})$
00000000000101	0000000037	$((1^{*2})^{3})+45$
00000000000102	0000000038	$((1+2)^{*3})+45$
00000000000103	0000000039	$((12+3)^{*4}-5)$
00000000000104	0000000040	$(12+3)+45$
00000000000105	0000000041	$((1+2)^{*3})^{*4}+5$
00000000000110	0000000042	$123-(4+5)$
00000000000111	0000000043	$((-1+23)+45)$
00000000000112	0000000044	$(1^{*23})+45$
00000000000113	0000000045	$(1+23)+45$
00000000000114	0000000046	$12^{*}((3/4)+5)$
00000000000115	0000000047	$1+(2^{*}(3+(4^{*5})))$
00000000000120	0000000048	$12^{*}((-3+4)+5)$
00000000000121	0000000049	$((12+3)^{*4}+5)$
00000000000122	0000000050	$(123+4)-5$
00000000000123	0000000051	$123^{*}(-4+5)$
00000000000124	0000000052	$(123-4)+5$
00000000000125	0000000053	$(12^{*3})+45$
00000000000130	0000000054	$(1^{*2})^{*}(34+5)$
00000000000131	0000000055	$1+(2^{*}(34+5)))$
00000000000132	0000000056	$((1+2)^{3})+45$
00000000000133	0000000057	$((-1-2)+((3^{*4})^{*5}))$
00000000000134	0000000058	$((1-2)+3)^{*45}$
00000000000135	0000000059	$((1+23)^{*4}-5)$
00000000000140	0000000060	$(123+4)+5$
00000000000141	0000000061	$(12^{*}(3+4))+5$
00000000000142	0000000062	$1234/5$
00000000000143	0000000063	$(-1+(2^{*}(3+45)))$
00000000000144	0000000064	$(1^{*2})^{*}(3+45)$
00000000000145	0000000065	$((1^{*23})^{*4}+5)$
00000000000150	0000000066	$(1+(23^{*4}))+5$
00000000000152	0000000068	$12+((3^{*4})^{*5})$
00000000000153	0000000069	$((1+23)^{*4}+5)$
00000000000154	0000000070	$((-12+34)^{*5})$
00000000000155	0000000071	$123+(4^{*5})$
00000000000200	0000000072	$((1^{*2})^{3})^{*}(4+5)$
00000000000201	0000000073	$1+((2^{3})^{*}(4+5))$

Base 6	Base 10	Increasing
00000000000202	0000000074	$((-1^2)+(3^4))-5$
00000000000203	0000000075	$((12+3)+4)^*5$
00000000000204	0000000076	$((1^2)*3)^4-5$
00000000000205	0000000077	$((1^2)+(3^4))-5$
00000000000210	0000000078	$(-12+(3^4))+5$
00000000000211	0000000079	$(-12+(3^4*5))$
00000000000212	0000000080	$(12+3+5)$
00000000000213	0000000081	$(1+2)^*(3+5)$
00000000000215	0000000083	$((-1-2)+(3^4))+5$
00000000000220	0000000084	$(12+(3^4))-5$
00000000000221	0000000085	$(-1^2)+(3^4*5)$
00000000000222	0000000086	$(1-2)+(3^4*5)$
00000000000223	0000000087	$((1^2)*3)^*45$
00000000000224	0000000088	$(-1+234)-5$
00000000000225	0000000089	$(1^*234)-5$
00000000000230	0000000090	$(1+234)-5$
00000000000231	0000000091	$((12*3)^4)-5$
00000000000234	0000000094	$(12+(3^4))+5$
00000000000235	0000000095	$(12+(3^4*5))$
00000000000240	0000000096	$(12*((3+4)+5))$
00000000000242	0000000098	$(-1+234)+5$
00000000000243	0000000099	$(1^*234)+5$
00000000000244	0000000100	$(1+234)+5$
00000000000245	0000000101	$((12^*3)^4)+5$
00000000000250	0000000102	$(-12+(34^5))$
00000000000251	0000000103	$((1+2)^3)^4-5$
00000000000253	0000000105	$((1-2)+34)^*5$
00000000000255	0000000107	$(-1-2)+(34^5)$
00000000000300	0000000108	$(-1^2)+(34^5)$
00000000000301	0000000109	$(1-2)+(34^5)$
00000000000302	0000000110	$((1^2)^34)^*5$
00000000000303	0000000111	$(1^2)+(34^5)$
00000000000304	0000000112	$(1^2)+(34^5)$
00000000000305	0000000113	$(1+2)+(34^5)$
00000000000311	0000000115	$((1^2)+34)^*5$
00000000000312	0000000116	$((1^2)+3)^*45$
00000000000314	0000000118	$(12+(34^5))$
00000000000315	0000000119	$(-1+((2+34)^5))$
00000000000320	0000000120	$((1^2)+34)^*5$
00000000000321	0000000121	$(1+((2+34)^5))$
00000000000322	0000000122	$((-1+(2^(3+4)))-5)$
00000000000323	0000000123	$((12^3)/4)-5$
00000000000324	0000000124	$(1+(2^(3+4)))-5$
00000000000325	0000000125	$((1+2)+34)^*5$
00000000000330	0000000126	$(-1+23)^*(4+5)$
00000000000331	0000000127	$(-1+(2^((3^4)-5)))$
00000000000332	0000000128	$((1/2)^3)^*(4^5)$
00000000000333	0000000129	$(-12+345)$
00000000000340	0000000132	$((-1+(2^(3+4)))+5)$
00000000000341	0000000133	$((12^3)/4)+5$
00000000000342	0000000134	$(-1-2)+345$
00000000000343	0000000135	$(-1^2)+345$
00000000000344	0000000136	$(12^*(34-5))$
00000000000345	0000000137	$(1^2)^*345$
00000000000350	0000000138	$(1^2)+345$
00000000000351	0000000139	$(1^2)+345$
00000000000352	0000000140	$(1+2)+345$
00000000000400	0000000144	$(1+23)^*(4+5)$
00000000000401	0000000145	$(12+345)$
00000000000402	0000000146	$(1+((2+3)^*45))$
00000000000410	0000000150	$(12+34)^*5$
00000000000411	0000000151	$(-1+(2*((3^4)-5)))$
00000000000412	0000000152	$(1^2)^*((3^4)-5)$
00000000000413	0000000153	$(1+(2*((3^4)-5)))$
00000000000415	0000000155	$((1+2)^3+4)^*5$
00000000000420	0000000156	$((-1+(2*(3^4)))-5)$
00000000000421	0000000157	$((1^2)^*(3^4))-5$
00000000000422	0000000158	$(1+(2*(3^4)))-5$
00000000000423	0000000159	$(-1+(((2^3)^4)^*5))$
00000000000424	0000000160	$((1^2)^3)^4)^*5$
00000000000425	0000000161	$(1+(((2^3)^4)^*5))$

Base 6	Base 10	Increasing
000000000000433	00000000165	$((1+((2^3)^4))^5)$
000000000000434	00000000166	$((-1+(2*(3^4)))+5)$
000000000000435	00000000167	$((1^2)*(3^4))+5)$
000000000000440	00000000168	$((1+(2*(3^4)))+5)$
000000000000443	00000000171	$((12^34)-5)$
000000000000444	00000000172	$((1^2)*((3^4)+5))$
000000000000445	00000000173	$((-1+((2^3)^45))$
000000000000450	00000000174	$((1+2)+3)^45)$
000000000000451	00000000175	$(1+((2^3)^45))$
000000000000500	00000000180	$((((1+2)^3)^4)^5)$
000000000000501	00000000181	$((12^34)+5)$
000000000000504	00000000184	$(12^*(3+(4^5)))$
000000000000531	00000000199	$((123^4)-5)$
000000000000535	00000000203	$((1+(2^3))^45)$
000000000000544	00000000208	$(12^*(-3+45))$
000000000000545	00000000209	$((123^4)+5)$
000000000000555	00000000215	$((-1+(2^34))^5)$
000000000001000	00000000216	$(12^*(34+5))$
000000000001003	00000000219	$((-1+((2^34)^5))$
000000000001004	00000000220	$((12+3)^4)^5)$
000000000001005	00000000221	$(1+((2^34)^5))$
000000000001013	00000000225	$((1+(2^34))^5)$
000000000001020	00000000228	$((1+2)*((3^4)-5))$
000000000001023	00000000231	$((-1+((2^3)^45))$
000000000001024	00000000232	$((1^2)^3)^45)$
000000000001025	00000000233	$(1+((2^3)^45))$
000000000001031	00000000235	$((123-4)^5)$
000000000001034	00000000238	$((1+2)*(3^4))-5)$
000000000001042	00000000242	$((-1+((2-3)+4)^5))$
000000000001043	00000000243	$((-1^23)+4)^5)$
000000000001044	00000000244	$(1+((2-3)+4)^5))$
000000000001052	00000000248	$((1+2)*(3^4))+5)$
000000000001055	00000000251	$((1^2+3)^4)-5)$
000000000001104	00000000256	$(12^*(3+45))$
000000000001110	00000000258	$((1+2)*((3^4)+5))$
000000000001111	00000000259	$((-1+((2^3)^4)/5)$
000000000001113	00000000261	$((1+2)^3)^45)$
000000000001133	00000000273	$((-1+(2^345))$
000000000001134	00000000274	$((1^2)^345)$
000000000001135	00000000275	$((123+4)^5)$
000000000001144	00000000280	$((12^*(3+4))^5)$
000000000001211	00000000295	$((-1+(23^4))^5)$
000000000001215	00000000299	$((-1+((23^4)^5))$
000000000001220	00000000300	$((1^23)^4)^5)$
000000000001221	00000000301	$(1+((23^4)^5))$
000000000001225	00000000305	$(1234-5)$
000000000001243	00000000315	$(1234+5)$
000000000001251	00000000319	$((12+3)^45)$
000000000001252	00000000320	$((1+23)^4)^5)$
000000000001310	00000000330	$((1+2)^34)^5)$
000000000001405	00000000365	$((-12+(3^4))^5)$
000000000001450	00000000390	$((-1-2)+(3^4))^5)$
000000000001454	00000000394	$((-1-((2-3^4))^5))$
000000000001455	00000000395	$((-1^2)+(3^4))^5)$
000000000001500	00000000396	$(1-((2-3^4))^5))$
000000000001501	00000000397	$((-12+((3^4)^5))$
000000000001504	00000000400	$((1-2)+(3^4))^5)$
000000000001510	00000000402	$((-1-2)+((3^4)^5))$
000000000001511	00000000403	$((-1^2)+((3^4)^5))$
000000000001512	00000000404	$((1-2)+((3^4)^5))$
000000000001513	00000000405	$((1^2)^3)^4)^5)$
000000000001514	00000000406	$((-1+23)^45)$
000000000001515	00000000407	$((1^2)+((3^4)^5))$
000000000001520	00000000408	$((1+2)+((3^4)^5))$
000000000001522	00000000410	$((1^2)+(3^4))^5)$
000000000001523	00000000411	$((1+2)^345)$
000000000001525	00000000413	$(12+((3^4)^5))$
000000000001530	00000000414	$((-1+((2+(3^4))^5))$
000000000001531	00000000415	$((1^2)+(3^4))^5)$
000000000001532	00000000416	$(1+((2+(3^4))^5))$
000000000001540	00000000420	$((1+2)+(3^4))^5)$

Base 6	Base 10	Increasing
00000000002002	0000000434	$(-1+(23^*45))$
00000000002003	0000000435	$((1^*23)^*45)$
00000000002004	0000000436	$(1+(23^*45))$
00000000002021	0000000445	$((12+(3^*4))^*5)$
00000000002043	0000000459	$(123^*(4+5))$
00000000002052	0000000464	$((1+23)^*45)$
00000000002053	0000000465	$((-1+234)^*5)$
00000000002101	0000000469	$(-1+(234^*5))$
00000000002102	0000000470	$((1^*234)^*5)$
00000000002103	0000000471	$(1+(234^*5))$
00000000002111	0000000475	$((1+234)^*5)$
00000000002120	0000000480	$((12^*3)^*4)^*5)$
00000000002123	0000000483	$((12^*3)-45)$
00000000002140	0000000492	$((12^*3)-(4^*5))$
00000000002155	0000000503	$((12^*3)-(4+5))$
00000000002211	0000000511	$((12^*3)+4)^*5)$
00000000002212	0000000512	$((-12^*3)+(4^*5))$
00000000002213	0000000513	$((12^*3)-4)^*5)$
00000000002225	0000000521	$((12^*3)+4)^*5)$
00000000002244	0000000532	$((12^*3)+(4^*5))$
00000000002300	0000000540	$((1+2)^*3)^*4)^*5)$
00000000002301	0000000541	$((12^*3)+45)$
00000000002344	0000000568	$(-1+2345)$
00000000002345	0000000569	(1^*2345)
00000000002350	0000000570	$(1+2345)$
00000000002452	0000000608	$(12^*((3^*4)-5))$
00000000002511	0000000619	$((-1+((2+3)^*4))-5)$
00000000002512	0000000620	$((12-3)^*4)^*5)$
00000000002513	0000000621	$(1+((2+3)^*4))-5)$
00000000002525	0000000629	$((-1+((2+3)^*4))+5)$
00000000002530	0000000630	$((12-3)^*4)^*5)$
00000000002531	0000000631	$(1+((2+3)^*4))+5)$
00000000002535	0000000635	$((-1+(2^*(3+4)))^*5)$
00000000002543	0000000639	$(-1+((2^*(3+4))^*5))$
00000000002544	0000000640	$((12^*3)/4)^*5)$
00000000002545	0000000641	$(1+((2^*(3+4))^*5))$
00000000002551	0000000643	$((12^*(3^*4))-5)$
00000000002553	0000000645	$(1+(2^*(3+4)))^*5)$
00000000003005	0000000653	$((12^*(3^*4))+5)$
00000000003104	0000000688	$(12^*((3^*4)+5))$
00000000003120	0000000696	$((12^*3)^*45)$
00000000003213	0000000729	$((1+2)^*((-3+4)+5))$
00000000003343	0000000783	$((1+2)^*3)^*45)$
00000000003421	0000000805	$((-1+(2^*(3^*4)))^*5)$
00000000003425	0000000809	$(-1+((2^*(3^*4))^*5))$
00000000003430	0000000810	$((1^*2)^*(3^*4))^*5)$
00000000003431	0000000811	$(1+((2^*(3^*4))^*5))$
00000000003435	0000000815	$(1+(2^*(3^*4)))^*5)$
00000000003443	0000000819	$((-1+(2^*(3^*4)))/5)$
00000000004024	0000000880	$(12^*34)^*5)$
00000000004052	0000000896	$((1-(2^*-3))^*(4^*5))$
00000000004301	0000000973	$(-123+(4^*5))$
00000000004341	0000000997	$(((-1-2)^*3)+(4^*5))$
00000000004344	0000001000	$((-12^*3)+(4^*5))$
00000000004400	0000001008	$((-1-23)+(4^*5))$
00000000004401	0000001009	$((-1^*23)+(4^*5))$
00000000004402	0000001010	$((1-23)+(4^*5))$
00000000004405	0000001013	$((-12-3)+(4^*5))$
00000000004411	0000001015	$((1+2)^*-3)+(4^*5))$
00000000004412	0000001016	$((-1^*2)^*3)+(4^*5))$
00000000004413	0000001017	$((1-(2^*3))^*(4^*5))$
00000000004414	0000001018	$((-1^*2)^*3)+(4^*5))$
00000000004415	0000001019	$((-12+3)+(4^*5))$
00000000004420	0000001020	$((123^*4)^*5)$
00000000004421	0000001021	$((1-2)^*3)+(4^*5))$
00000000004422	0000001022	$((1^*2)-3)+(4^*5))$
00000000004423	0000001023	$((-1^*23)+(4^*5))$
00000000004424	0000001024	$((1+23)/4)^*5)$
00000000004425	0000001025	$((1^*23)+(4^*5))$
00000000004430	0000001026	$((1-2)+3)+(4^*5))$
00000000004431	0000001027	$((1^*2)^*3)+(4^*5))$

Base 6	Base 10	Increasing
00000000004432	00000001028	$((1^2)+3)+(4^5)$
00000000004433	00000001029	$((12-3)+(4^5))$
00000000004434	00000001030	$((1+2)+3)+(4^5)$
00000000004435	00000001031	$((1+(2^3))+3)+(4^5)$
00000000004440	00000001032	$((1^2)^3+3)+(4^5)$
00000000004441	00000001033	$((1+2)^3+3)+(4^5)$
00000000004443	00000001035	$((12+3)+3)+(4^5)$
00000000004450	00000001038	$((-1+23)+3)+(4^5)$
00000000004451	00000001039	$((1^*23)+3)+(4^5)$
00000000004452	00000001040	$((1+23)+3)+(4^5)$
00000000004504	00000001048	$((12^*3)+3)+(4^5)$
00000000004511	00000001051	$((1+2)^3+3)+(4^5)$
00000000004551	00000001075	$(123+3)+(4^5)$
00000000005024	00000001096	(12^*345)
00000000005200	00000001152	$((1+(2^3-3))^3)+(4^5)$
00000000005343	00000001215	$((1+2)^3+(3^4))^5$
00000000005532	00000001280	$((1^2+3)^4+3)^5$
00000000005550	00000001290	$((-1+((2^3)^4))-5)$
00000000005551	00000001291	$((1+2+3)^4-5)$
00000000005552	00000001292	$((1+((2^3)^4))-5)$
000000000010004	00000001300	$((-1+((2^3)^4))+5)$
000000000010005	00000001301	$((1+2+3)^4+5)$
000000000010010	00000001302	$((1+((2^3)^4))+5)$
000000000010503	00000001479	(123^*45)
000000000011040	00000001536	$((12^3)+3)+(4^5)$
000000000011102	00000001550	(1234^*5)
000000000012345	00000001865	12345
000000000013241	00000002041	$((-1-(2*(3-(4^5))))))$
000000000013242	00000002042	$((1^2)^*(3+(4^5)))$
000000000013243	00000002043	$((12^3)^4-5)$
000000000013252	00000002048	$((1-2)+3)^3+(4^5)$
000000000013301	00000002053	$((12^3)^4+5)$
000000000013302	00000002054	$((1^2)^*(3+(4^5)))$
000000000013303	00000002055	$(1+(2*(3+(4^5))))$
000000000014034	00000002182	$((1+2)^(3+4))-5$
000000000014043	00000002187	$((1+2)^(3^4))-5$
000000000014052	00000002192	$((1+2)^(3+4))+5$
000000000015032	00000002396	$((1+(2^3))^4)-5$
000000000015050	00000002406	$((1+(2^3))^4+5)$
000000000015432	00000002540	$((12^3)-4)^5$
000000000015504	00000002560	$((-1/2)+3)^3+(4^5)$
000000000015540	00000002580	$((12^3)+4)^5$
000000000022103	00000003063	$((1+2)^*(3+(4^5)))$
000000000022104	00000003064	$((-12+(3*(4^5))))$
000000000022113	00000003069	$((-1-2)+(3*(4^5)))$
000000000022114	00000003070	$((-1^2)+(3*(4^5)))$
000000000022115	00000003071	$((1-2)+(3*(4^5)))$
000000000022120	00000003072	$((1^2)^3)^3+(4^5)$
000000000022121	00000003073	$((1^2)+(3*(4^5)))$
000000000022122	00000003074	$((1^2)+(3*(4^5)))$
000000000022123	00000003075	$((1+2)+(3*(4^5)))$
000000000022132	00000003080	$(12+(3*(4^5)))$
000000000022133	00000003081	$((1+2)^*(3+(4^5)))$
000000000022240	00000003120	$((-1+((2+3)^4))^5)$
000000000022244	00000003124	$((-1+((2+3)^4))^5)$
000000000022245	00000003125	$((1^23)+4)^5$
000000000022250	00000003126	$(1+((2+3)^4))^5$
000000000022254	00000003130	$(1+((2+3)^4))^5$
000000000023000	00000003240	$(12^*(3^4))^5$
000000000024332	00000003584	$((1/2)+3)^3+(4^5)$
000000000030534	00000004090	$((-1+(2^(3^4))))-5$
000000000030535	00000004091	$((1^2)^(3^4))-5$
000000000030540	00000004092	$((1+(2^(3^4))))-5$
000000000030543	00000004095	$((-1+(2^((3+4)+5))))$
000000000030544	00000004096	$(12^((3-4)+5))$
000000000030545	00000004097	$(1+(2^((3+4)+5)))$
000000000030552	00000004100	$((-1+(2^(3^4))))+5$
000000000030553	00000004101	$((1^2)^(3^4))+5$
000000000030554	00000004102	$((1+(2^(3^4))))+5$
000000000033200	00000004608	$(12^3)^*(4+5)$
000000000035411	00000005119	$((-1+((2+3)^3))^5)$

Base 6	Base 10	Increasing
000000000035412	00000005120	$((12-3)*(4^5))$
000000000035413	00000005121	$(1+((2+3)*(4^5)))$
000000000044235	00000006143	$(-1+((2^3)*(4^5)))$
000000000044240	00000006144	$((1+2)+3*(4^5))$
000000000044241	00000006145	$(1+((2^3)*(4^5)))$
000000000045551	00000006475	$((-1+((2^3)^4))^5)$
000000000045555	00000006479	$(-1+(((2^3)^4)^5))$
000000000050000	00000006480	$((1+2)+3^4)^5$
000000000050001	00000006481	$(1+((2^3)^4)^5)$
000000000050005	00000006485	$(1+((2^3)^4))^5$
000000000050204	00000006556	$((1+2)^3)^4-5$
000000000050222	00000006566	$((1+2)^3)^4+5$
000000000053104	00000007168	$(1+(2^3))^4$
000000000055555	00000007775	$(-1+((2/(3^4))^-5))$
000000000100000	00000007776	$((12^3/4)^5)$
000000000100001	00000007777	$(1+((2/(3^4))^-5))$
000000000101452	00000008168	$(12^* (-3+(4^5)))$
000000000101531	00000008191	$(-1+((2^3)^4)^5)$
000000000101532	00000008192	$((1^2)^3)^4$
000000000101533	00000008193	$(1+(2^3)^4)^5$
000000000102012	00000008216	$(12^*(3+(4^5)))$
000000000110400	00000009216	$((1+2)^3)^4$
000000000114512	00000010124	$(-1+((23^4)/5))$
000000000114513	00000010125	$((1^23)^4)/5$
000000000114514	00000010126	$(1+((23^4)/5))$
000000000115224	00000010240	$((12^3)^4)^5$
000000000122343	00000010935	$((1+2)^(3+4))^5$
000000000124052	00000011264	$(12+3)^4$
000000000131325	00000012005	$((1+(2^3))^4)^5$
000000000150212	00000014336	$(-1+23)^4$
000000000151432	00000014636	$((12+3)^4)-5$
000000000151450	00000014646	$((12+3)^4)+5$
000000000152424	00000014848	$(12^3)^4$
000000000155035	00000015359	$(-1+(23^*(4^5)))$
000000000155040	00000015360	$(1^*23)^4$
000000000155041	00000015361	$(1+(23^*(4^5)))$
000000000203504	00000016384	$(1+23)^4$
000000000205435	00000016799	$(-12+((3+4)^5))$
000000000205444	00000016804	$((-1-2)+((3+4)^5))$
000000000205445	00000016805	$(-1^*2)+((3+4)^5)$
000000000205450	00000016806	$(1-2)+((3+4)^5)$
000000000205451	00000016807	$((12+3)-4)^5$
000000000205452	00000016808	$(1^2)+((3+4)^5)$
000000000205453	00000016809	$(1^*2)+((3+4)^5)$
000000000205454	00000016810	$(1+2)+((3+4)^5)$
000000000205503	00000016815	$(12+((3+4)^5))$
000000000231031	00000019675	$(-12+(3^4)^5)$
000000000231040	00000019680	$((-1-2)+(3^4)^5)$
000000000231041	00000019681	$(-1^*2)+(3^4)^5$
000000000231042	00000019682	$(1-2)+(3^4)^5$
000000000231043	00000019683	$((1^2)^3)^4$
000000000231044	00000019684	$(1^2)+(3^4)^5$
000000000231045	00000019685	$(1^*2)+(3^4)^5$
000000000231050	00000019686	$(1+2)+(3^4)^5$
000000000231055	00000019691	$(12+(3^4)^5)$
000000000234443	00000020475	$((-1+(2^3)^4))^5$
000000000234451	00000020479	$(-1+((2^3)^4)^5)$
000000000234452	00000020480	$((1^2)^3)^4$
000000000234453	00000020481	$(1+((2^3)^4))^5$
000000000234501	00000020485	$(1+(2^3)^4))^5$
000000000305440	00000024576	$(12^3)^4$
000000000332000	00000027648	$((1+2)^3)^4$
000000000411412	00000032768	$(12^*(-3+4))^5$
000000000411513	00000032805	$((1+2)^3)^4$
000000000415341	00000033613	$(-1+(2^*((3+4)^5)))$
000000000415342	00000033614	$(1^*2)^*((3+4)^5)$
000000000415343	00000033615	$(1+(2^*((3+4)^5)))$
000000000453455	00000038411	$((1-23)^4)-5$
000000000453513	00000038421	$((1-23)^4)+5$
000000000502125	00000039365	$(-1+(2^*(3^4)^5)))$
000000000502130	00000039366	$(1^*2)^*(3^4)^5$

Base 6	Base 10	Increasing
00000000502131	00000039367	$(1+(2*(3^{(4+5))))$
000000001025233	00000050421	$((1+2)*((3+4)^5))$
000000001030203	00000050619	$((-1+(23^4))-5)$
000000001030204	00000050620	$((1*23)^4-5)$
000000001030205	00000050621	$((1+(23^4))-5)$
000000001030221	00000050629	$((-1+(23^4))+5)$
000000001030222	00000050630	$((1*23)^4+5)$
000000001030223	00000050631	$((1+(23^4))+5)$
000000001041440	00000052224	$(123*(4^5))$
000000001133212	00000059048	$(-1+(((2+3)+4)^5))$
000000001133213	00000059049	$((12-3)+4)^5$
000000001133214	00000059050	$(1+(((2+3)+4)^5))$
000000001223215	00000065531	$((1+23)^4-5)$
000000001223233	00000065541	$((1+23)^4+5)$
000000001322525	00000073205	$((12+3)^4)*5$
000000002050543	00000099999	$(-1+(((2*3)+4)^5))$
000000002050544	00000100000	$((-1+23)-4)^5$
000000002050545	00000100001	$(1+(((2*3)+4)^5))$
000000002400000	00000124416	$(1/2)*((3^4)^5)$
000000002450451	00000131071	$(-1+(2^{(34-5))))$
000000002450452	00000131072	$(1*2)^{(34-5)}$
000000002450453	00000131073	$(1+(2^{(34-5))))$
000000002514252	00000134456	$(12*(3+4)^5)$
000000003213000	00000157464	$(12*(3^{(4+5))))$
000000003241334	00000161050	$(-1+((23-4)^5))$
000000003241335	00000161051	$((1/2)*34^5)$
000000003241340	00000161052	$(1+((23-4)^5))$
000000004041132	00000192080	$((1-23)^4)*5$
000000005155544	00000248824	$(-12+((3^4)^5))$
000000005155553	00000248829	$((-1-2)+((3^4)^5))$
000000005155554	00000248830	$((-1*2)+((3^4)^5))$
000000005155555	00000248831	$((1-2)+((3^4)^5))$
000000005200000	00000248832	$((1+23)-4)^5$
000000005200001	00000248833	$(1+(((2^3)+4)^5))$
000000005200002	00000248834	$(1*2)+((3^4)^5)$
000000005200003	00000248835	$(1+2)+((3^4)^5)$
000000005200012	00000248840	$(12+((3^4)^5))$
000000005231504	00000253120	$((-1+(23^4))^5)$
000000005231512	00000253124	$(-1+((23^4))^5)$
000000005231513	00000253125	$((1*23)^4)*5$
000000005231514	00000253126	$(1+((23^4))^5)$
000000005231522	00000253130	$(1+(23^4))^5$
000000005341344	00000262144	$(12^{(-3+4)+5})$
000000011005012	00000327680	$((1+23)^4)*5$
000000011035551	00000331771	$((12*3)^4)-5$
000000011040005	00000331781	$((12*3)^4)+5$
000000011542541	00000371293	$((1+2)*3+4)^5$
000000014355555	00000497663	$(-1+(2*((3^4)^5)))$
000000014400000	00000497664	$(1*2)*((3^4)^5)$
000000014400001	00000497665	$(1+(2*((3^4)^5)))$
000000015123132	00000524288	$(12^3)^*(4^5)$
000000015220204	00000531436	$((1+2)^{(3^4)})-5$
000000015220213	00000531441	$(1+2)^{(3+4)+5}$
000000015220222	00000531446	$((1+2)^{(3^4)})+5$
000000015305531	00000537823	$(-1+((2+(3^4))^5))$
000000015305532	00000537824	$(-12+34)^5$
000000015305533	00000537825	$(1+((2+(3^4))^5))$
000000024000000	00000746496	$(1+2)*((3^4)^5)$
000000024135343	00000759375	$((12+3)+4)^5$
000000025551341	00000838861	$(1+(2^34))/5$
000000034250304	00001048576	$((1^2)+3)^4*5$
000000055320000	00001658880	$((12*3)^4)*5$
000000104300000	00001889568	$((-1+23)+4)^5$
000000105510124	00001953124	$(-1+((2+3)^{(4+5))))$
000000105510125	00001953125	$(12-3)^{(4+5)}$
000000105510130	00001953126	$(1+((2+3)^{(4+5))))$
000000110400000	00001990656	$(12*(3^4)^5)$
000000112541003	00002097147	$(12^{(3+4)})-5$
000000112541012	00002097152	$(12^{(3^4)})-5$
000000112541021	00002097157	$(12^{(3+4)})+5$
000000125023230	00002476098	$(-1+((23+4)^5))$

Base 6	Base 10	Increasing
000000125023231	00002476099	$((1*23)+4)^5$
000000125023232	00002476100	$(1+((23+4)^5))$
000000131121412	00002576816	$(1/2)*(34^5)$
000000132541513	00002657205	$((1+2)^{(3*4)})^5$
000000152330451	00003199999	$(-1-((2-34)^5))$
000000152330452	00003200000	$(12+(3*4)^5)$
000000152330453	00003200001	$(1-((2-34)^5))$
000000223311513	00004084101	$((1-2)+34)^5$
000000225522014	00004194298	$(-1+(2^34))-5$
000000225522015	00004194299	$((1^2)^34)-5$
000000225522020	00004194300	$(1+(2^34))-5$
000000225522032	00004194308	$(-1+(2^34))+5$
000000225522033	00004194309	$((1^2)^34)+5$
000000225522034	00004194310	$(1+(2^34))+5$
000000302243212	00005153624	$(-12+(34^5))$
000000302243221	00005153629	$(-1-2)+(34^5)$
000000302243222	00005153630	$(-1^2)+(34^5)$
000000302243223	00005153631	$(1-2)+(34^5)$
000000302243224	00005153632	$((1^2)^34)^5$
000000302243225	00005153633	$(1^2)+(34^5)$
000000302243230	00005153634	$(1^*2)+(34^5)$
000000302243231	00005153635	$(1+2)+(34^5)$
000000302243240	00005153640	$12+(34^5)$
000000345541515	00006436343	$((1^2)+34)^5$
000000401000204	00006765196	$(123^4)-5$
000000401000222	00006765206	$(123^4)+5$
000000442355555	00007962623	$(-1+((2+34)^5))$
000000442400000	00007962624	$((1^2)+34)^5$
000000442400001	00007962625	$1+((2+34)^5)$
000000455444051	00008388607	$(-1+(2^(3+(4*5))))$
000000455444052	00008388608	$(1^*2)^(3+(4*5))$
000000455444053	00008388609	$(1+(2^(3+(4*5))))$
000000545151121	00009765625	$((1+2)+34)^5$
000000555555555	00010077695	$(-1+((2*3)^(4+5)))$
000001000000000	00010077696	$((1+2)+3)^(4+5)$
000001000000001	00010077697	$(1+((2*3)^(4+5)))$
000001004530451	00010307263	$(-1+(2*(34^5)))$
000001004530452	00010307264	$(1^*2)*(34^5)$
000001004530453	00010307265	$(1+(2*(34^5)))$
000001012425104	00010485760	$(12^(3+4))^5$
000001231314043	00014348907	$((1+2)/(3^4))^5$
000001311214120	00015460896	$(1+2)*(34^5)$
000001412513344	00017210368	$((12^3)+4)^5$
000002025254203	00020971515	$(-1+(2^34))^5$
000002025254211	00020971519	$(-1+((2^34)^5))$
000002025254212	00020971520	$((1^2)^34)^5$
000002025254213	00020971521	$(1+((2^34)^5))$
000002025254221	00020971525	$(1+(2^34))^5$
000002224500000	00024300000	$(12+34)^5$
000002501342211	00028629151	$((1+2)^3+4)^5$
000003155104331	00033554431	$(-1+(((2^3)^4)^5))$
000003155104332	00033554432	$((1^2)^3)^4)^5$
000003155104333	00033554433	$(1+(((2^3)^4)^5))$
000003205001513	00033826005	$(123^4)^5$
000003514450213	00039135393	$(1+((2^3)^4))^5$
000004000530131	00040353607	$(1+(2^3)^(4+5))$
000004031403132	00041229056	$12*(34^5)$
000010000000000	00060466176	$((1+2)^3)^4)^5$
000010354213103	00067108863	$(-1+(2^(-3+45)))$
000010354213104	00067108864	$(1/2)^(3-45)$
000010354213105	00067108865	$1+(2^(-3+45))$
000020451531043	00129140163	$(1+2)^(34-5)$
000021152430211	00134217727	$(-1+(2^(34+5)))$
000021152430212	00134217728	$(1^*2)^(34+5)$
000021152430213	00134217729	$(1+(2^(34+5)))$
000022330522351	00147008443	$(-1+(2^34))^5$
000024210421011	00164916223	$(-1+((2^34)^5))$
000024210421012	00164916224	$((12+3)^4)^5$
000024210421013	00164916225	$(1+((2^34)^5))$
000030151024513	00184528125	$(1+(2^34))^5$
000034431354235	00229345007	$(123-4)^5$

Base 6	Base 10	Increasing
000102235433213	00387420489	$((1+2)^3)^{(4+5)}$
000121535044131	00503284375	$((123+4)^5)$
000125135001252	00536870912	$((1-2)+3)^{45}$
000130352032052	00550731776	$(12^*(3+4))^5$
000154535150415	00714924299	$(-1+(23^4))^5$
000205054355555	00777599999	$(-1+((23^4)^5))$
000205054400000	00777600000	$((1^*23)^4)^5$
000205054400001	00777600001	$(1+((23^4)^5))$
000215450344021	00844596301	$(1+(23^4))^5$
000254314002544	01073741824	$((1+23)^4)^5$
000324133500000	01252332576	$((1+2)^*34)^5$
000541413041401	02073071593	$(-12+(3^4))^5$

Base 6	Base 10	Decreasing
00000000000002	0000000002	$((5^4)/32)+1$
00000000000003	0000000003	$(5/((4/(3^2))+1))$
00000000000004	0000000004	$((5+(4^3))-21)$
00000000000005	0000000005	$(-54+(3^21))$
00000000000010	0000000006	$(5*((4/32)+1))$
00000000000011	0000000007	$(54-(3^(2+1)))$
00000000000012	0000000008	$((5*(-4+3))+21)$
00000000000013	0000000009	$((-5+43)-21)$
00000000000014	0000000010	$((5^4)+3)-21)$
00000000000015	0000000011	$((5-(4+3))+21)$
00000000000020	0000000012	$(((-5+43)/2)+1)$
00000000000021	0000000013	$(54-(32+1))$
00000000000022	0000000014	$((54-32)*1)$
00000000000023	0000000015	$((54-32)+1)$
00000000000024	0000000016	$((5+43)/2)*1)$
00000000000025	0000000017	$((5+43)/2)+1)$
00000000000030	0000000018	$(54-(3+21))$
00000000000031	0000000019	$((5+43)-21)$
00000000000032	0000000020	$((5/4)*(3+21))$
00000000000033	0000000021	$((5-4)+32)*1)$
00000000000034	0000000022	$((5-4)+32)+1)$
00000000000035	0000000023	$((-5+43)+2)-1)$
00000000000040	0000000024	$((5+43)-21)$
00000000000041	0000000025	$((5/4)^32)*1)$
00000000000042	0000000026	$((5/4)^32)+1)$
00000000000043	0000000027	$(54-((3^2)+1))$
00000000000044	0000000028	$(54-((3+2)+1))$
00000000000045	0000000029	$((5+4)+32)*1)$
00000000000050	0000000030	$((5+4)+32)+1)$
00000000000051	0000000031	$((5+43)-2)+1)$
00000000000052	0000000032	$((5+43)*(2-1))$
00000000000053	0000000033	$((54-3)+2)*1)$
00000000000054	0000000034	$(54^3)/(2+1))$
00000000000055	0000000035	$((-5+43)+21)$
00000000000100	0000000036	$((5^4)+3)+21)$
00000000000101	0000000037	$((5+43)*(2-1))$
00000000000102	0000000038	$((5+43)+2)-1)$
00000000000103	0000000039	$((5+43)+2)*1)$
00000000000104	0000000040	$((5+43)+2)+1)$
00000000000105	0000000041	$((5+43)^2)+1)$
00000000000110	0000000042	$((5+43)^2)-1)$
00000000000111	0000000043	$(54+(3*(2+1)))$
00000000000112	0000000044	$((54-3)+21)$
00000000000113	0000000045	$((5+43)+21)$
00000000000114	0000000046	$((-5+(4^3))-21)$
00000000000115	0000000047	$((5^4)^3)-21)$
00000000000120	0000000048	$((5+4)+(3^21))$
00000000000121	0000000049	$((-5+(43^2))^*1)$
00000000000122	0000000050	$((5+43)+21)$
00000000000123	0000000051	$((54^3)/2)*1)$
00000000000124	0000000052	$((54^3)/2)+1)$
00000000000125	0000000053	$((5+432)-1)$
00000000000130	0000000054	$((5+432)^*1)$
00000000000131	0000000055	$((5+432)+1)$
00000000000132	0000000056	$((5+(4^3))-21)$
00000000000133	0000000057	$((5^4)^3)-(2+1))$
00000000000134	0000000058	$((5+(43^2))-1)$
00000000000135	0000000059	$((5+(43^2))^*1)$
00000000000140	0000000060	$((5+(43^2))+1)$
00000000000141	0000000061	$(54+(3^(2+1)))$
00000000000142	0000000062	$((54-3)^2)*1)$
00000000000143	0000000063	$((54-3)^2)+1)$
00000000000144	0000000064	$((5+43)^2)*1)$
00000000000145	0000000065	$((5+43)^2)+1)$
00000000000150	0000000066	$((-5+43)*(2+1))$
00000000000151	0000000067	$((5+(4^3))-2)^*1)$
00000000000152	0000000068	$(54*((3-2)+1))$
00000000000153	0000000069	$(543/(2+1))$
00000000000154	0000000070	$(5*(43-21))$
00000000000155	0000000071	$((-5+(4*(32-1))))$
00000000000200	0000000072	$((-5+(4^3))+21)$

Base 6	Base 10	Decreasing
00000000000201	0000000073	$(54+(3*21))$
00000000000202	0000000074	$((54+3)*2)*1$
00000000000203	0000000075	$((54+3)*2)+1$
00000000000204	0000000076	$(-5+(43*(2+1)))$
00000000000210	0000000078	$((5+4)-3)*21$
00000000000211	0000000079	$(-5+(4*(32+1)))$
00000000000212	0000000080	$(5*(-4+32))*1$
00000000000213	0000000081	$(5+(4*(32-1)))$
00000000000214	0000000082	$(5+(4^3))+21$
00000000000220	0000000084	$(5+(4*32))-1$
00000000000221	0000000085	$54*((3/2)+1)$
00000000000222	0000000086	$(5+(43*(2+1)))$
00000000000223	0000000087	$(-54+321)$
00000000000225	0000000089	$(54*3)-21$
00000000000230	0000000090	$(5+4)*(-3+21)$
00000000000231	0000000091	$(-5+(4*3))*21$
00000000000233	0000000093	$(54-3)*(2+1)$
00000000000235	0000000095	$5*((4*(3+2))-1)$
00000000000240	0000000096	$(5+43)*(2+1)$
00000000000243	0000000099	$(54*3)-(2+1)$
00000000000244	0000000100	$5*((4+3)+21)$
00000000000245	0000000101	$(-5*4)+321$
00000000000250	0000000102	$(54*3)*(2-1)$
00000000000251	0000000103	$((54*3)+2)-1$
00000000000252	0000000104	$((54*3)+2)*1$
00000000000253	0000000105	$((54*3)+2)+1$
00000000000303	0000000111	$(54+3)*(2+1)$
00000000000304	0000000112	$(-5-4)+321$
00000000000305	0000000113	$(5+(4*(3^2+1)))$
00000000000311	0000000115	$(54*3)+21$
00000000000313	0000000117	$((-5+(4^3))*2)-1$
00000000000314	0000000118	$((-5+(4^3))*2)*1$
00000000000315	0000000119	$(5*(4+32))-1$
00000000000320	0000000120	$(-5+4)+321$
00000000000321	0000000121	$(5-4)*321$
00000000000322	0000000122	$(5*43)-21$
00000000000323	0000000123	$(-5+((4^3)*2))*1$
00000000000324	0000000124	$(5*(43-2))-1$
00000000000325	0000000125	$5*((4+32)+1)$
00000000000330	0000000126	$(5*(43-2))+1$
00000000000334	0000000130	$(5+4)+321$
00000000000340	0000000132	$(5*43)-(2+1)$
00000000000341	0000000133	$((5*43)-2)*1$
00000000000342	0000000134	$((5*43)-2)+1$
00000000000343	0000000135	$(5*43)*(2-1)$
00000000000344	0000000136	$54*((3+2)-1)$
00000000000345	0000000137	$((5*43)+2)*1$
00000000000350	0000000138	$((5*43)+2)+1$
00000000000351	0000000139	$((5+(4^3))*2)+1$
00000000000352	0000000140	$5*((43+2)-1)$
00000000000353	0000000141	$(5*4)+321$
00000000000355	0000000143	$((5+4)+3)^2-1$
00000000000400	0000000144	$(5+4)*(3+21)$
00000000000401	0000000145	$(5*(43+2))*1$
00000000000402	0000000146	$(5*(43+2))+1$
00000000000404	0000000148	$(5*43)+21$
00000000000405	0000000149	$(5+((4*3)^2))*1$
00000000000410	0000000150	$5*((43+2)+1)$
00000000000411	0000000151	$(-5+((4*3)*21))$
00000000000415	0000000155	$(54+321)$
00000000000420	0000000156	$((5+4)+3)*21$
00000000000422	0000000158	$(-5+432)-1$
00000000000423	0000000159	$(-5+432)*1$
00000000000424	0000000160	$(-5+432)+1$
00000000000425	0000000161	$(5+((4*3)*21))$
00000000000433	0000000165	$5*((4^3)/2)+1$
00000000000440	0000000168	$(5+432)-1$
00000000000441	0000000169	$(5+432)*1$
00000000000442	0000000170	$(5+432)+1$
00000000000443	0000000171	$(54*(3+2))+1$
00000000000451	0000000175	$5*(-4+(3*21))$

Base 6	Base 10	Decreasing
000000000000453	00000000177	$((-5+(4^3))^*(2+1))$
000000000000455	00000000179	$((5+4)^*32)-1$
000000000000500	00000000180	$((5+4)^*32)*1$
000000000000501	00000000181	$((5+4)^*32)+1$
000000000000505	00000000185	$(5*((4*(3^2))+1))$
000000000000511	00000000187	$(-5+((4^3)*(2+1)))$
000000000000513	00000000189	$((5+4)^*(32+1))$
000000000000522	00000000194	$(543-21)$
000000000000525	00000000197	$(5+((4^3)*(2+1)))$
000000000000532	00000000200	$(5*(43+21))$
000000000000535	00000000203	$((54*3)^*2)-1$
000000000000540	00000000204	$(543-(2+1))$
000000000000541	00000000205	$((543-2)*1)$
000000000000542	00000000206	$((543-2)+1)$
000000000000543	00000000207	$(543*(2-1))$
000000000000544	00000000208	$((543+2)-1)$
000000000000545	00000000209	$((543+2)*1)$
000000000000550	00000000210	$((543+2)+1)$
000000000000555	00000000215	$(5*(4+(3*21)))$
0000000000001000	00000000216	$((5+4)-3)^(2+1))$
0000000000001004	00000000220	$(543+21)$
0000000000001005	00000000221	$(5+(4*3))^*21$
0000000000001034	00000000238	$(54*((3*2)+1))$
0000000000001040	00000000240	$(5*((4+3)^2)-1))$
0000000000001043	00000000243	$((5+4)*(3^(2+1)))$
0000000000001044	00000000244	$(5*((4+3)^2))-1$
0000000000001045	00000000245	$(5*((4+3)^2))*1$
0000000000001050	00000000246	$(5*((4+3)^2))+1$
0000000000001054	00000000250	$(5*((4+3)^2)+1))$
0000000000001055	00000000251	$(-5+(4^((3+2)-1)))$
0000000000001103	00000000255	$(5*((4^3)-21))$
0000000000001113	00000000261	$(5+(4^((3+2)-1)))$
0000000000001121	00000000265	$(5*((43*2)-1))$
0000000000001125	00000000269	$((5*43)^*2)-1$
0000000000001130	00000000270	$((5*43)^*2)*1$
0000000000001131	00000000271	$((5*43)^*2)+1$
0000000000001132	00000000272	$(54*((3^2)-1))$
0000000000001135	00000000275	$(5*((43*2)+1))$
0000000000001154	00000000286	$((-5+43)^*21)$
0000000000001200	00000000288	$((5+(4*3))^2)-1$
0000000000001201	00000000289	$((5+(4*3))^2)*1$
0000000000001202	00000000290	$((5+(4*3))^2)+1$
0000000000001215	00000000299	$((5*4)+3)^*21$
0000000000001225	00000000305	$(54*(3^2))-1$
0000000000001230	00000000306	$(54*3)^*(2+1))$
0000000000001231	00000000307	$(54*(3^2))+1$
0000000000001233	00000000309	$(5*((4^3)-2))-1$
0000000000001234	00000000310	$(5*((4^3)-2))*1$
0000000000001235	00000000311	$(5*((4^3)-2))+1$
0000000000001240	00000000312	$((5^4)-3)/2)+1$
0000000000001241	00000000313	$((5^4+3)/2)-1$
0000000000001242	00000000314	$((5^4+3)/2)*1$
0000000000001243	00000000315	$((5^4+3)/2)+1$
0000000000001245	00000000317	$(5*(4^3))-(2+1))$
0000000000001250	00000000318	$((5*(4^3))-2)*1$
0000000000001251	00000000319	$((5*(4^3))-2)+1$
0000000000001252	00000000320	$(5*4)*(3+21))$
0000000000001253	00000000321	$((5*(4^3))+2)-1$
0000000000001254	00000000322	$((5*(4^3))+2)*1$
0000000000001255	00000000323	$((5*(4^3))+2)+1$
0000000000001301	00000000325	$(5*((4^3)+2))-1$
0000000000001305	00000000329	$(5*((4^3)+2))-1$
0000000000001310	00000000330	$(5*((4^3)+2))*1$
0000000000001311	00000000331	$(5*((4^3)+2))+1$
0000000000001313	00000000333	$(5*(4^3))+21$
0000000000001315	00000000335	$(5*((4^3)+2)+1))$
0000000000001322	00000000338	$(-5+((4+3)^(2+1)))$
0000000000001324	00000000340	$(54*(-3+21))$
0000000000001331	00000000343	$((-5+(4*3))^(2+1))$
0000000000001334	00000000346	$(-5+(43*21))$
0000000000001340	00000000348	$(5+((4+3)^(2+1)))$

Base 6	Base 10	Decreasing
000000000001343	00000000351	$((5+4)^3)^*21$
000000000001352	00000000356	$(5+(43^*21))$
000000000001432	00000000380	$(5^4)^*(32-1)$
000000000001441	00000000385	$5*((4^3)+21)$
000000000001455	00000000395	$5*((4^*32)-1)$
000000000001503	00000000399	$((5^4)^*32)-1$
000000000001504	00000000400	$((5^4)^*32)^*1$
000000000001505	00000000401	$((5^4)^*32)+1$
000000000001511	00000000403	$(54-3)^*21$
000000000001513	00000000405	$(5^43)^*(2+1)$
000000000001525	00000000413	$(543^*2)-1$
000000000001530	00000000414	$(543^*2)^*1$
000000000001531	00000000415	$(543^*2)+1$
000000000001532	00000000416	$(5+43)^*21$
000000000001540	00000000420	$(5^4)^*(32+1)$
000000000002035	00000000455	$(5*(4+3))^*21$
000000000002115	00000000479	$(-5+(4^*321))$
000000000002121	00000000481	$(54+3)^*21$
000000000002123	00000000483	$((5-43)^2)-1$
000000000002124	00000000484	$((5-43)^2)^*1$
000000000002125	00000000485	$((5-43)^2)+1$
000000000002133	00000000489	$5+(4^*321)$
000000000002200	00000000504	$(5^4)-321$
000000000002240	00000000528	$((5^4+3)^2)-1$
000000000002241	00000000529	$((5^4+3)^2)^*1$
000000000002242	00000000530	$((5^4+3)^2)+1$
000000000002300	00000000540	$(5^4)^*(3^2+1)$
000000000002304	00000000544	$54*(3+21)$
000000000002413	00000000585	$5*(-4+321)$
000000000002414	00000000586	$(5^4)-(3^*21)$
000000000002434	00000000598	$(5^4)-(3^2+1)$
000000000002444	00000000604	$(5^4)-(32+1)$
000000000002445	00000000605	$((5^4)-32)^*1$
000000000002450	00000000606	$((5^4)-32)+1$
000000000002453	00000000609	$(5^4)-(3+21)$
000000000002503	00000000615	$((5^4)+3)-21$
000000000002504	00000000616	$(5^4)-(3^2+1)$
000000000002505	00000000617	$((5^4)-(3^2)+1)$
000000000002510	00000000618	$(5^4)-((3^2)+1)$
000000000002511	00000000619	$(5^4)-((3+2)+1)$
000000000002512	00000000620	$((5^4)-(3+2))^*1$
000000000002513	00000000621	$543*(2+1)$
000000000002514	00000000622	$((5^4)-3)^*(2-1)$
000000000002515	00000000623	$((5^4)-3)+2-1$
000000000002520	00000000624	$((5^4)-3)+2)^*1$
000000000002521	00000000625	$5*(4+321)$
000000000002522	00000000626	$(5^4)+(3/(2+1))$
000000000002523	00000000627	$((5^4+3)-2)+1$
000000000002524	00000000628	$((5^4+3)^*(2-1))$
000000000002525	00000000629	$((5^4+3)+2)-1$
000000000002530	00000000630	$((5^4+3)+2)^*1$
000000000002531	00000000631	$((5^4+3)+2)+1$
000000000002532	00000000632	$((5^4)+(3^2)+1)$
000000000002533	00000000633	$((5^4)+(3^2))-1$
000000000002534	00000000634	$(5^4)+(3^2+1)$
000000000002535	00000000635	$((5^4)-3)+21$
000000000002543	00000000639	$((5*(4^3))^*2)-1$
000000000002544	00000000640	$((5*(4^3))^*2)^*1$
000000000002545	00000000641	$((5^4)+3)+21$
000000000002552	00000000644	$((5^4)+32)-1$
000000000002553	00000000645	$((5^4)+32)^*1$
000000000002554	00000000646	$54*(32-1)$
000000000003004	00000000652	$(5^4)+(3^2+1)$
000000000003024	00000000664	$(5^4)+(3^*21)$
000000000003051	00000000679	$(54^*32)-1$
000000000003052	00000000680	$(54^*32)^*1$
000000000003053	00000000681	$(54^*32)+1$
000000000003150	00000000714	$54*(32+1)$
000000000003151	00000000715	$5*((4^3)^2)-1$
000000000003152	00000000716	$((5+4)^3)-21$
000000000003155	00000000719	$(5*((4^3)^2))-1$

Base 6	Base 10	Decreasing
00000000003200	0000000720	$((5*((4*3)^2))*1)$
00000000003201	0000000721	$((5*((4*3)^2))+1)$
00000000003203	0000000723	$((-5+(43^2))-1)$
00000000003204	0000000724	$((-5+(43^2))*1)$
00000000003205	0000000725	$((-5+(43^2))+1)$
00000000003210	0000000726	$((5+4)^3-(2+1))$
00000000003211	0000000727	$((((5+4)^3)-2)*1)$
00000000003212	0000000728	$((((5+4)^3)^2)-1)$
00000000003213	0000000729	$((((5+4)^3)^2)*1)$
00000000003214	0000000730	$((((5+4)^3)^2)+1)$
00000000003215	0000000731	$((((5+4)^3)+2)*1)$
00000000003220	0000000732	$((((5+4)^3)+2)+1)$
00000000003221	0000000733	$((5+(43^2))-1)$
00000000003222	0000000734	$((5+(43^2))*1)$
00000000003223	0000000735	$((5+(43^2))+1)$
00000000003234	0000000742	$((5+4)^3+21)$
00000000003242	0000000746	$((5^4)+321)$
00000000003315	0000000767	$((-5+(4^3))*21)$
00000000003340	0000000780	$((5^4)^3)^21)$
00000000003435	0000000815	$(5^*(432-1))$
00000000003443	0000000819	$(5^*432)-1)$
00000000003444	0000000820	$(5^*432)^*1)$
00000000003445	0000000821	$(5^*432)+1)$
00000000003453	0000000825	$(5^*(432+1))$
00000000003455	0000000827	$(-5+((4^3)^21))$
00000000003513	0000000837	$(5+((4^3)^21))$
00000000004053	0000000897	$((5+(4^3))^21)$
00000000004130	0000000918	$(54^*(3^(2+1)))$
00000000004240	0000000960	$((54-3)^2)-1)$
00000000004241	0000000961	$((54-3)^2)^*1)$
00000000004242	0000000962	$((54-3)^2)+1)$
00000000004312	0000000980	$(-5+4321)$
00000000004330	0000000990	$(5+4321)$
00000000004414	0000001018	$((-5+(4^(3+2))))-1)$
00000000004415	0000001019	$((-5+(4^(3+2))))^*1)$
00000000004420	0000001020	$((-5+(4^(3+2))))+1)$
00000000004423	0000001023	$((5+43)^2)-1)$
00000000004424	0000001024	$((5+43)^2)^*1)$
00000000004425	0000001025	$((5+43)^2)+1)$
00000000004432	0000001028	$((5+(4^(3+2))))-1)$
00000000004433	0000001029	$((5+(4^(3+2))))^*1)$
00000000004434	0000001030	$((5+(4^(3+2))))+1)$
00000000005013	0000001089	$((5+4)^321)$
00000000005204	0000001156	$(54^((3-2)+1))$
00000000005400	0000001224	$((5^*(4+3))^2)-1)$
00000000005401	0000001225	$((5^*(4+3))^2)^*1)$
00000000005402	0000001226	$((5^*(4+3))^2)+1)$
00000000005431	0000001243	$(5432-1)$
00000000005432	0000001244	$(5432)^*1)$
00000000005433	0000001245	$(5432+1)$
00000000005442	0000001250	$((5^4)^*((3-2)+1))$
00000000005451	0000001255	$((((5^4)+3)^2)-1)$
00000000005452	0000001256	$((((5^4)+3)^2)^*1)$
00000000005453	0000001257	$((((5^4)+3)^2)+1)$
00000000005532	0000001280	$(5^*(4^((3+2)-1)))$
000000000010050	0000001326	$((54^3)^21)$
000000000010200	0000001368	$((54+3)^2)-1)$
000000000010201	0000001369	$((54+3)^2)^*1)$
000000000010202	0000001370	$((54+3)^2)+1)$
000000000010425	0000001457	$((((5+4)^3)^2)-1)$
000000000010430	0000001458	$((((5+4)^3)^2)^*1)$
000000000010431	0000001459	$((((5+4)^3)^2)+1)$
000000000011535	0000001715	$(5^*((4+3)^(2+1)))$
000000000011551	0000001723	$(-5+((4^3)^(2+1)))$
000000000012000	0000001728	$((5+4+3)^(2+1))$
000000000012005	0000001733	$(5+((4^3)^(2+1)))$
000000000012043	0000001755	$(5^*43)^21)$
000000000012342	0000001862	$((5^4)^3)-21)$
000000000012350	0000001866	$((5^4)-3)^*(2+1))$
000000000012400	0000001872	$((5^4)^3)-(2+1))$
000000000012401	0000001873	$((5^4)^3)-2)^*1)$

Base 6	Base 10	Decreasing
00000000012402	0000001874	$((5^4)^3 - 2) + 1$
00000000012403	0000001875	$((5^4)^3)^*(2-1)$
00000000012404	0000001876	$((5^4)^3 + 2) - 1$
00000000012405	0000001877	$((5^4)^3 + 2)^*1$
00000000012410	0000001878	$((5^4)^3 + 2) + 1$
00000000012420	0000001884	$((5^4) + 3)^*(2+1)$
00000000012424	0000001888	$((5^4)^3) + 21$
00000000014043	0000002187	$((5+4)^3)^*(2+1)$
00000000015112	0000002420	$(5^4)^*321$
00000000015324	0000002500	$(5^4)^*((3+2) - 1)$
00000000020243	0000002691	543^*21
00000000022244	0000003124	$((5^4)^*(3+2)) - 1$
00000000022245	0000003125	$5^*(4/32)^{-1}$
00000000022250	0000003126	$((5^4)^*(3+2)) + 1$
00000000024040	0000003480	$((5 - 4^3)^2) - 1$
00000000024041	0000003481	$((5 - 4^3)^2)^*1$
00000000024042	0000003482	$((5 - 4^3)^2) + 1$
00000000024355	0000003599	$((5^4)^3)^2 - 1$
00000000024400	0000003600	$((5^4)^3)^2^*1$
00000000024401	0000003601	$((5^4)^3)^2 + 1$
00000000024504	0000003640	$5^*(43^2) - 1$
00000000024512	0000003644	$(5^*(43^2)) - 1$
00000000024513	0000003645	$(5^*(43^2))^*1$
00000000024514	0000003646	$(5^*(43^2)) + 1$
00000000024522	0000003650	$5^*(43^2) + 1$
00000000025205	0000003749	$((5^4)^3)^2 - 1$
00000000025210	0000003750	$(5^4)^*((3+2) + 1)$
00000000025211	0000003751	$((5^4)^3)^2 + 1$
00000000030303	0000003999	$((5^4)^3/2) - 1$
00000000030304	0000004000	$((5^4)^3/2)^*1$
00000000030305	0000004001	$((5^4)^3/2) + 1$
00000000030534	0000004090	$(-5 + (4^3)^2) - 1$
00000000030535	0000004091	$(-5 + (4^3)^2) + 1$
00000000030540	0000004092	$(-5 + (4^3)^2)^*1$
00000000030552	0000004100	$(5 + (4^3)^2) - 1$
00000000030553	0000004101	$(5 + (4^3)^2)^*1$
00000000030554	0000004102	$(5 + (4^3)^2) + 1$
00000000031014	0000004114	54^*321
00000000031132	0000004160	$(5^*(4^3))^*21$
00000000032131	0000004375	$(5^4)^*((3^2) + 1)$
00000000034012	0000004760	$((5 + (4^3)^2) - 1)$
00000000034013	0000004761	$((5 + (4^3)^2)^*1)$
00000000034014	0000004762	$((5 + (4^3)^2) + 1)$
00000000034425	0000004913	$(5 + (4^3)^2)^*(2+1)$
00000000034445	0000004925	5^*4321
00000000035052	0000005000	$(5^4)^*((3^2) - 1)$
00000000035403	0000005115	$5^*((4^3)^2) - 1$
00000000035411	0000005119	$(5^*(4^3)^2) - 1$
00000000035412	0000005120	$(5^*(4^3)^2)^*1$
00000000035413	0000005121	$(5^*(4^3)^2) + 1$
00000000035421	0000005125	$5^*((4^3)^2) + 1$
00000000042012	0000005624	$((5^4)^*(3^2) - 1)$
00000000042013	0000005625	$((5^4)^3)^*(2+1)$
00000000042014	0000005626	$((5^4)^*(3^2)) + 1$
00000000044534	0000006250	$(5^4)^*(-3+21)$
00000000050213	0000006561	$(5+4)^*((3+2) - 1)$
00000000054321	0000007465	54321
00000000100551	0000007987	$((5^4)^3) - 21$
00000000101005	0000007997	$((5^4)^3) - (2+1)$
00000000101010	0000007998	$((5^4)^3 - 2)^*1$
00000000101011	0000007999	$((5^4)^3 - 2) + 1$
00000000101012	0000008000	$((5^4)^3)^*(2-1)$
00000000101013	0000008001	$((5^4)^3 + 2) - 1$
00000000101014	0000008002	$((5^4)^3 + 2)^*1$
00000000101015	0000008003	$((5^4)^3 + 2) + 1$
00000000101033	0000008013	$((5^4)^3) + 21$
00000000101234	0000008086	$((5^4) - 3)^*21$
00000000101444	0000008164	$((5^4) + 3)^*21$
00000000101532	0000008192	$((-5+4)+3)^21$
00000000104000	0000008640	$5^*((4^3)^2)^*(2+1)$
00000000111513	0000009477	$((5+4)^3)^*21$

Base 6	Base 10	Decreasing
000000000114144	00000010000	$((5^4)^*(3+21))$
000000000120055	00000010403	$((54*3)^2)-1$
000000000120100	00000010404	$((54*3)^2)*1$
000000000120101	00000010405	$((54*3)^2)+1$
000000000121144	00000010648	$((-5+43)^{(2+1)})$
000000000130551	00000011875	$((5^4)^*(32-1))$
000000000132155	00000012167	$((5^4+3)^{(2+1)})$
000000000133511	00000012499	$((5^4)^*32)-1$
000000000133512	00000012500	$((5^4)^*32)*1$
000000000133513	00000012501	$((5^4)^*32)+1$
000000000140433	00000013125	$((5^4)^*(32+1))$
000000000200200	00000015624	$((5^{\wedge}(4*3)/2))-1$
000000000200201	00000015625	$(5^{\wedge}((-4-3)+21))$
000000000200202	00000015626	$((5^{\wedge}(4*3)/2))+1$
000000000202023	00000015999	$((5^4)^3)^2)-1$
000000000202024	00000016000	$((5^4)^3)^2)*1$
000000000202025	00000016001	$((5^4)^3)^2)+1$
000000000203455	00000016379	$(-5+(4^{\wedge}((3^2)+1)))$
000000000203513	00000016389	$(5+(4^{\wedge}((3^2)+1)))$
000000000210043	00000016875	$((5^4)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
000000000220212	00000018224	$((5*43)^2)-1$
000000000220213	00000018225	$((5*43)^2)*1$
000000000220214	00000018226	$((5*43)^2)+1$
000000000230551	00000019651	$((54^3)/2)-1$
000000000230552	00000019652	$((54^3)/2)*1$
000000000230553	00000019653	$((54^3)/2)+1$
000000000231034	00000019678	$(-5+(43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
000000000231043	00000019683	$((5+4)^3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
000000000231052	00000019688	$(5+(43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
000000000234443	00000020475	$(5^*(4^{\wedge}(3^2))-1)$
000000000234451	00000020479	$(5^*(4^{\wedge}(3^2)))-1$
000000000234452	00000020480	$(5^*(4^{\wedge}((3+2)+1)))$
000000000234453	00000020481	$(5^*(4^{\wedge}(3^2)))+1$
000000000234501	00000020485	$(5^*((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1))$
000000000303040	00000024000	$((5^4)^3)^*(2+1))$
000000000304503	00000024375	$((5^4)^3)^*21$
000000000304531	00000029791	$((54-3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
000000000411412	00000032768	$((5+43)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
000000000501523	00000039291	$((54^3)-21)$
000000000501541	00000039301	$((54^3)-(2+1))$
000000000501542	00000039302	$((54^3)-2)*1$
000000000501543	00000039303	$((54^3)-2)+1$
000000000501544	00000039304	$((54^3)^*(2-1))$
000000000501545	00000039305	$((54^3)+2)-1$
000000000501550	00000039306	$((54^3)+2)*1$
000000000501551	00000039307	$((54^3)+2)+1$
000000000502005	00000039317	$((54^3)+21)$
0000000005030212	00000042848	$((543^2)-1)$
0000000005030213	00000042849	$((543^2)*1)$
0000000005030214	00000042850	$((543^2)+1)$
0000000005030255	00000042875	$(5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1))$
0000000001030301	00000050653	$((54+3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
0000000001133212	00000059048	$((5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$
0000000001133213	00000059049	$((5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2))*1$
0000000001133214	00000059050	$((5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2))+1$
0000000001223215	00000065531	$(-5+(4^{\wedge}((3^2)-1)))$
0000000001223233	00000065541	$(5+(4^{\wedge}((3^2)-1)))$
0000000001342041	00000075625	$((5^4)^*321)$
0000000001401344	00000078112	$((5^{\wedge}(4+3))-21)$
0000000001401402	00000078122	$((5^{\wedge}(4+3))-(2+1))$
0000000001401403	00000078123	$((5^{\wedge}(4+3))-2)*1$
0000000001401404	00000078124	$((5^{\wedge}(4+3))-2)+1$
0000000001401405	00000078125	$(5^{\wedge}(((4*3)/2)+1))$
0000000001401410	00000078126	$((5^{\wedge}(4+3))+2)-1$
0000000001401411	00000078127	$((5^{\wedge}(4+3))+2)*1$
0000000001401412	00000078128	$((5^{\wedge}(4+3))+2)+1$
0000000001401430	00000078138	$((5^{\wedge}(4+3))+21)$
0000000001403531	00000078607	$((54^3)^2)-1$
0000000001403532	00000078608	$((54^3)^2)*1$
0000000001403533	00000078609	$((54^3)^2)+1$
0000000001431132	00000081920	$(5^*(4^{\wedge}((3^2)+1)))$

Base 6	Base 10	Decreasing
000000002035343	00000098415	$(5*(43^{(2+1)}))$
000000002110023	00000102399	$((5*(4^3))^2)-1$
000000002110024	00000102400	$((5*(4^3))^2)*1$
000000002110025	00000102401	$((5*(4^3))^2)+1$
000000002121252	00000104000	$((5^4)^3)*21$
000000002305520	00000117912	$(54^3)*(2+1)$
000000003203213	00000156249	$((5^{(4+3)})^2)-1$
000000003203214	00000156250	$((5^{(4+3)})^2)*1$
000000003203215	00000156251	$((5^{(4+3)})^2)+1$
000000003232424	00000160000	$(5^4)^{(3+2)-1}$
000000004222455	00000205379	$(-5+(4^3))^{(2+1)}$
000000004344000	00000216000	$((5^4)*3)^{(2+1)}$
000000005005023	00000234375	$(5^{(4+3)})*(2+1)$
000000005341334	00000262138	$(-5+(4^{(3^2)}))-1$
000000005341335	00000262139	$(-5+(4^{(3*(2+1))}))$
000000005341340	00000262140	$(-5+(4^{(3^2)}))+1$
000000005341352	00000262148	$(5+(4^{(3^2)}))-1$
000000005341353	00000262149	$(5+(4^{(3*(2+1))}))$
000000005341354	00000262150	$(5+(4^{(3^2)}))+1$
000000011005012	00000327680	$(5*(4^{(3^2)-1}))$
000000011012513	00000328509	$(5+(4^3))^{(2+1)}$
000000012143043	00000386883	$((5^4)-3)^2-1$
000000012143044	00000386884	$((5^4)-3)^2*1$
000000012143045	00000386885	$((5^4)-3)^2+1$
000000012212240	00000390624	$(5^{(4^{(3/2))})}-1$
000000012212241	00000390625	$(5^{(4^{(3/2))})}*1$
000000012212242	00000390626	$(5^{(4^{(3/2))})}+1$
000000012241503	00000394383	$((5^4)+3)^2-1$
000000012241504	00000394384	$((5^4)+3)^2*1$
000000012241505	00000394385	$((5^4)+3)^2+1$
000000014541304	00000510952	$(54^3)*21$
000000015220212	00000531440	$((5+4)^{(3*2)})-1$
000000015220213	00000531441	$(5+4)^{(3+2)+1}$
000000015220214	00000531442	$((5+4)^{(3*2)})+1$
000000033433545	00001015625	$(5^{(4+3)})*21$
000000034250255	00001048571	$(-5+(4^{(-3+21)}))$
000000034250313	00001048581	$(5+(4^{(-3+21)}))$
000000034425000	00001061208	$(54^3)^{(2+1)}$
000000044032043	00001310715	$(5*(4^{(3^2)}))-1$
000000044032051	00001310719	$(5*(4^{(3^2)}))-1$
000000044032052	00001310720	$(5*(4^{(3*(2+1))}))$
000000044032053	00001310721	$(5*(4^{(3^2)}))+1$
000000044032101	00001310725	$(5*(4^{(3^2)}))+1$
000000044350424	00001336336	$(54^{(3+2)-1})$
000000054054122	00001593698	$(-5^4)+(3^21)$
000000054100545	00001594289	$(-54+(3^21))$
000000054101011	00001594303	$(-5^4)+(3^21)$
000000054101030	00001594314	$(-5-4)+(3^21)$
000000054101042	00001594322	$(-5+4)+(3^21)$
000000054101043	00001594323	$((5+4)/3)^21$
000000054101044	00001594324	$(5-4)+(3^21)$
000000054101100	00001594332	$(5+4)+(3^21)$
000000054101115	00001594343	$(5^4)+(3^21)$
000000054101141	00001594357	$(54+(3^21))$
000000054104004	00001594948	$(5^4)+(3^21)$
000000105510124	00001953124	$(5^{(4+3)+2})-1$
000000105510125	00001953125	$(5^{(43/(2+1))})$
000000105510130	00001953126	$(5^{(4+3)+2})+1$
000000124422343	00002460375	$(5^43)^{(2+1)}$
000000152330451	00003199999	$((5^4)^{(3+2)})-1$
000000152330452	00003200000	$((5^4)^{(3+2)})*1$
000000152330453	00003200001	$((5^4)^{(3+2)})+1$
000000203204012	00003515624	$((5^4)*3)^2-1$
000000203204013	00003515625	$((5^4)*3)^2*1$
000000203204014	00003515626	$((5^4)*3)^2+1$
000000250303213	00004782969	$(5+4)^{(3*2)+1}$
000000304212332	00005242880	$(5/(4^{(3-21)}))$
000000344404251	00006377287	$(-5+(4*(3^21)))$
000000344404305	00006377297	$(5+(4*(3^21)))$
000000442505311	00007971595	$(5*(-4+(3^21)))$
000000442505415	00007971635	$(5*(4+(3^21)))$

Base 6	Base 10	Decreasing
000000514035343	00008869743	$(543^{(2+1)})$
000000545151120	00009765624	$((5^{(4+(3^2))})-1)$
000000545151121	00009765625	$(5^{((4+3)+2)+1})$
000000545151122	00009765626	$((5^{(4+(3^2))})+1)$
000001231314043	00014348907	$((5+4)*(3^{21}))$
000003055234300	00031886460	$((5^4)*(3^{21}))$
000003130155412	00032768000	$((5*(4^3))^{(2+1)})$
000004134350213	00043046721	$((5+4)^{(3^2)-1})$
000004301501103	00045435423	$((54^{(3+2)})-1)$
000004301501104	00045435424	$((54^{(3+2)})^*1)$
000004301501105	00045435425	$((54^{(3+2)})+1)$
000004502320045	00048828125	$(5^{((4+(3^2))+1)})$
000005213502130	00054206982	$(54*(3^{21}))$
000010203424143	00063999999	$((5^4)^{(3^2)-1})$
000010203424144	00064000000	$((5^4)^{(3+2)+1})$
000010203424145	00064000001	$((5^4)^{(3^2))+1)$
000010354213104	00067108864	$((5-4)+3)^{21}$
000035513442344	00240641848	$((5^4-3)^{(2+1)})$
000040120440340	00244140612	$(5^{(4*3)}-21)$
000040120440354	00244140622	$(5^{(4*3)}-(2+1))$
000040120440355	00244140623	$((5^{(4*3)}-2)^*1)$
000040120440400	00244140624	$((5^{(4*3)}-2)+1)$
000040120440401	00244140625	$(5^{((-4+3)+21)})$
000040120440402	00244140626	$((5^{(4*3)}+2)-1)$
000040120440403	00244140627	$((5^{(4*3)}+2)^*1)$
000040120440404	00244140628	$((5^{(4*3)}+2)+1)$
000040120440422	00244140638	$(5^{(4*3)}+21)$
000040324254544	00247673152	$((5^4+3)^{(2+1)})$
000102235433212	00387420488	$((5+4)^{(3^2)}-1)$
000102235433213	00387420489	$(5+4)^{(3*(2+1))}$
000102235433214	00387420490	$((5+4)^{(3^2))+1)$
000120241321201	00488281249	$((5^{(4*3)})^2-1)$
000120241321202	00488281250	$((5^{(4*3)})^2)^*1)$
000120241321203	00488281251	$((5^{(4*3)})^2)+1)$
000200402202003	00732421875	$(5^{(4*3)})^{(2+1)}$
000242513231043	00996451875	$(5^4)*(3^{21})$
000321043523204	01220703124	$(5^{(4+(3^2))}-1)$
000321043523205	01220703125	$(5*(4-3))^{21}$
000321043523210	01220703126	$(5^{(4+(3^2))})+1)$
000331002501532	01280000000	$(5^4)^{(3^2)+1)$
000413142304143	01544804415	$(54^{(3^2)}-1)$
000413142304144	01544804416	$(54^{(3+2)+1})$
000413142304145	01544804417	$(54^{(3^2)})+1)$